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Report on improved and upscaled understanding of how behaviour and behavioural change can support transformation to more sustainable socio-ecological forest systems and better biodiversity status at multiple spatial levels.

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Index

Index.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Methodology.....	5
2.1. Models.....	5
2.2. Scenarios.....	5
3. Germany.....	7
3.1. Methods.....	7
3.2. Scenario results and interpretation.....	11
3.3. Main findings.....	20
4. Spain.....	21
4.1. Methods.....	21
4.2. Scenario results and interpretation.....	26
4.3. Main findings.....	31
5. Sweden.....	33
5.1. Methods.....	33
5.2. Scenario results and interpretation.....	37
5.3. Main findings.....	41
6. European Union.....	43
6.1. Methods.....	43
6.2. Scenario results and interpretation.....	46
6.3. Main findings.....	54
7. Synthesis.....	57
References.....	58
Annex I: Scenario storylines for the Spanish case study.....	61
Scenario 1 (Multifunctional / BAU).....	61
Scenario 2 (Closer-to-nature management).....	61

1. Introduction

Despite ambitious policy targets at the global and EU levels, biodiversity is under increasing threat (Leclere et al. 2020; Pereira et al. 2024). Ambitious policy targets have been set to halt the loss of biodiversity. Still, effective implementation depends, among other factors, on supportive behavioural responses from forest owners and conservation managers who must respond to multiple policy and socio-economic drivers, forcing them to make decisions and trade-offs while dealing with complexity and uncertainty (Deuffic et al. 2018). Previous research suggests that cross-sectoral goal conflicts, as well as failures to understand behavioural responses, constitute major barriers to achieving desired forest biodiversity outcomes (Beland Lindahl et al. 2017; Sotirov et al. 2019).

The complex nature of human decision-making has been the focus of studies for decades across several themes, including environmental modeling (Groeneveld et al., 2017). Many socio-ecological factors shape forest management decisions and lead to different behavioural responses. There are various types of forest owners and managers, hereafter collectively called 'agents', with a range of objectives, preferences, and behaviours that influence forest management decision-making. It is crucial to consider these differences in behaviour and behavioural change in forest management decision support tools when evaluating the impact of policies, market drivers, and conservation goals on forest environments (e.g., see Sotirov et al., 2019).

Maximo et al. (2025) recently described how certain biophysical forest models have been improved in representing the behaviour and behavioural change of forest owners and managers. Rather than adding human agency to forest models through scenarios, Maximo et al. (2025) integrated human behaviour and behavioural change into four forest simulation models. They did this based on a survey conducted by Sotirov et al. (2025a) and by analyzing the main management practices used by different forest owner and manager typologies (agents) and the factors influencing their decision-making.

Building on the work by Maximo et al. (2025), the current study aimed to examine how behaviour and behavioural change can support improvements in forest biodiversity status and, more generally, in more sustainable socio-ecological forest systems, including synergies and trade-offs, by quantitatively assessing the outcomes of selected policy and management scenarios.

2. Methodology

2.1. Models

In this study, we build on four forest models (EFISCEN-space, FORMES, HEUREKA and G4M) that have been improved by Maximo et al. (2025) with regard to the representation of behaviour and behavioural change of forest owners and managers for case studies across Europe (Table 1.1). For a more detailed description of the models and the improvements made to them, we refer to Maximo et al. 2025 or the references given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Overview of models used in this study (updated from Maximo et al 2025).

	Germany	Spain	Sweden	EU
Model	EFISCEN-space	FORMES	HEUREKA	G4M + FLAM
Reference	Schelhaas et al. 2022	Trasobares et al. 2022	Lämås et al. 2023	Kindermann et al. 2013
Spatial resolution and coverage	Plot / regional, Baden-Württemberg and North Rhein Westphalia	Regional, Catalonia	Regional, Norrbotten County	Grid, EU-27
Temporal coverage	~2020-2100	2020-2050	~2020-2120 (or shorter)	~2020-2050
Forest and ecosystem service indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing stock wood removals carbon stocks and storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing stock wood removals carbon stocks and storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing stock wood removals carbon stocks and storage annual growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing stock wood removals carbon stocks and storage burned areas
Biodiversity indicators*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of forest with uneven-aged structure Stock of organic carbon Share of forest dominated by native tree species Tree species diversity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tree microhabitats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadwood Share of forest dominated by more than one tree species Tree species diversity Share of forest with uneven-aged structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadwood Species richness Broadleaf forests Veteran trees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standing deadwood Lying deadwood Share of forest dominated by native tree species Tree species diversity

*Biodiversity indicators have been identified based on indicators specified in the EU Nature Restoration regulation (article 12 and Annex V1).

2.2. Scenarios

Three contrasting explorative “what-if” future policy scenarios at the EU-level were developed (Sotirov et al., 2025b). The policy scenarios envisioned how forest policy could evolve by 2050 and described both end-states and the processes leading to them. Each scenario describes alternative developments in social, technological, environmental, economic, and policy factors, which resulted in policy pathways with different priorities for regulatory vs. economic instruments (Sotirov et al., 2025b). The three scenarios can be summarized as follows (Haase et al. in prep.):

- **Biodiversity First:** The EU prioritizes biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration with strict forest protection laws and a shift towards close-to-nature forestry. 30% of EU forests are protected and clear-cutting is banned on all lands, promoting natural regeneration and increased forest connectivity. Carbon sequestration focuses on storing carbon in forests rather than harvested wood products. Timber production is reduced, but alternative payments for ecosystem services (e.g., carbon storage, recreation) support forest owners.
- **Multifunctionality:** The EU balances economic growth, biodiversity protection, and carbon neutrality, creating forests that provide multiple ecosystem services. Sustainable timber production, selective logging, and reforestation coexist with protected areas and carbon sequestration goals. Policies mix regulations with market incentives, supporting both forest conservation and renewable energy from bio-based materials. Bioenergy, timber, and biodiversity goals are pursued simultaneously, aiming for economic stability while maintaining ecological integrity.
- **Wood Bioeconomy First:** The EU prioritises economic growth and energy security with forests managed intensively for timber, bioenergy, and bioplastics. Clear-cutting, fast-growing monocultures, and genetically modified trees are widely used to meet increasing global demand. EU policies focus on boosting domestic timber production, reducing imports, and expanding the biomass energy sector aimed to drive the forest-based economy.

These policy scenarios have been interpreted and implemented in the four models to quantify and assess impacts on key forest variables, biodiversity and ecosystem services (see Table 1.1). The implementation of the scenarios in each forest model is described in chapters 3-6.

The forest dynamics were simulated until 2050 and 2100 for two climate scenarios, i.e., Representative Concentration Pathways 4.5 and 8.5 (van Vuuren et al. 2011). RCP4.5 is considered an intermediate scenario of the expected changes in radiative forcing, leading to moderate greenhouse gas emissions and therefore a slight increase in global surface temperatures and the side-effects of climate change on ecosystems. RCP8.5 is the most extreme scenario as it is assumed that greenhouse gas emissions will continue to steadily rise throughout all the 21st century. It leads to the major increases in temperatures.

3. Germany

3.1. Methods

3.1.1. Scenarios and implementation

The scenario implementation for the German case study was built on the approach described by Maximo et al. (2025) for Baden-Württemberg and North Rhine-Westphalia, summarized in Figure 3.1. Maximo et al. (2025) developed (i) a model to spatially allocate agent typologies across the forest landscape for the two regions; (ii) a model to predict current forest management; (iii) a model to predict changes in forest management in favour of biodiversity; and (iv) a simplified equation to predict the occurrence of behavioural change. Models ii and iii rely on forest structure as input parameters, but also consider information on forest ownership and forest owner typology. Together, these components provided the stepping stones for predicting forest management practices, which served as the basis for simulating future forest resources using the EFISCEN-Space model.

Figure 3.1. Process flow diagram for the German case-study (Maximo et al., 2025).

In this case study, we combined EFISCEN-Space with the models by Maximo et al. (2025) to assess the outcomes of the *Biodiversity First* policy scenario (see Chapter 2). The *Multifunctionality* and *Wood Bioeconomy First* scenarios were not considered, as survey data on owner responses were not available to parameterize these scenarios. Instead, we

compared the *Biodiversity First* policy scenario with a Baseline management scenario, which is based on the continuation of harvest practices according to repeated forest inventory observations. In addition, we included a Current management scenario, which is based on stated harvest practices and tree species selection, as derived from the survey by Sotirov et al. 2025a. The three scenarios are described below and a summary is provided in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Summary of the scenarios covered in the German case study.

Scenario label	Climate-change scenario	Cutting regime	Tree species selection / regeneration method
Baseline 4.5	RCP4.5	Observed harvest regime retrieved from EFISCEN-Space Management Rule Database. The harvesting regime is defined by forest structure, with clear-cutting or partial cutting (i.e., group or single-tree selection).	Forest regeneration is only based on natural regeneration.
Baseline 8.5	RCP8.5		
Current 4.5	RCP4.5	Stated harvest management, according to survey responses for current forest management practices (Figure 2, A). Harvest is primarily based on single-tree selection, targeting trees with larger diameters.	Forest regeneration is mostly based on natural regeneration. Additional tree species are introduced into the stand in accordance with the stated planting activities.
Current 8.5	RCP8.5		
Biodiversity 4.5	RCP4.5	Stated management, according to survey responses for management practices to improve biodiversity (Figure 2, B). Harvest is mainly based on single tree (targeting bigger trees) and group selection (no specific diameter target).	Forest regeneration is mostly based on natural regeneration. Additional tree species are introduced into the stand in accordance with the stated planting activities.
Biodiversity 8.5	RCP8.5		

To implement the *Biodiversity First* policy scenario, the drivers defined in this scenario were compared to the surveyed 26 socio-economic factor influences decision-making for forest management (see chapter 3 Maximo et al. 2025 for details). Table 3.2 shows how the drivers in the “Biodiversity First” policy scenario were linked with corresponding socio-economic factors affecting the behaviour of agents. Climate change was also considered a driver in the *Biodiversity First* policy scenario, being its effects considered separately by applying EFISCEN-Space for two climate scenarios, as described in Chapter 2.

Table 3.2. Biodiversity First policy scenario (Sotirov et al. 2025b) and interpreted socio-economic factors (Sotirov et al. 2025a).

Drivers	Driver setting	Socio-economic factors
Societal changes	Environmentally concerned stagnating society with reduced consumption	NA
Economic changes	Low traditional economic growth with low energy and low material (biomass) consumption	Item 8: Timber prices
Policy changes	Priority for nature conservation and climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level mainly governed by regulatory tools, and partial support by subsidies	Item 2: Regulatory biodiversity policy (objectives, targets, standards in law and bylaw) Item 5: Economic instruments (subsidies, compensation payments, taxes)
Forest management prescriptions	Promotion of forest biodiversity conservation/restoration and carbon forest sinks objectives	Item 6: Informational instruments (advisory services, knowledge, research, know-how transfer) Item 17: Advice from a consultant, managing company or forest owner association that I am member of

Based on the mapping in Table 3.2, the behaviour change equation was used to estimate the probability that an agent, belonging to a specific typology group, decides to implement changes in their forest management according to the policy driver scenario. This equation relies on a combined probability distribution, utilizing the survey’s average responses by agent typology regarding the importance of each socio-economic item for forest management decisions (see chapter 3 by Maximo et al., 2025, for details). In practice, applying the behaviour change equation in this study serves as a theoretical approach, as the connection between socio-economic factors, policy drivers, and forest management forms a complex system. The developed function only offers a simple mathematical representation of this reality. Additionally, since survey respondents indicated high scores for most of the socio-economic factors covered, the probability of targeting a change is always very high. When applying the behaviour change equation to the Biodiversity First policy scenario and the five socio-economic factors shown in Table 3.2, it resulted in approximately a 99.9% probability of change for all agent typologies. Figure 3.2 shows the proportion of assigned harvesting practices among the simulated plots. On the left-hand (A) the stated management prescriptions for *current* conditions are shown and on the right-hand (B) the potential changes toward *biodiversity* gathered in the survey.

Figure 3.2. Changes in distribution of harvesting practices applied in the Current (A) and Biodiversity (B) scenario.

Besides the activities previously described, it was also necessary to set quantitative parameters for forest management approaches to enable forest resource simulations in EFISCEN-Space. Due to practical considerations involving survey data collection and distribution, the survey only captures forest management regimes as categorical labels, lacking specific quantitative information such as timing and intensity of silvicultural practices. Therefore, to address this gap, the stated management practices were linked to the EFISCEN-Space Forest Management Rule Database (Filipek et al. in prep; Feliciano et al. 2025) to describe current harvesting practices.

The Forest Management Rule Database is based on observed data on differences in wood volume from repeated forest inventories and structured according to dominant tree species and biogeographical location. This study relied on harvesting estimates derived from the repeated observations from Germany's 2nd and 3rd NFI, as reported by Filipek et al. (in prep). The approach considers the average probability and intensity of wood removal over a 12-year interval (the period between observations). For example, a plot dominated by Norway spruce in the continental biogeographical region has a 5% chance of being clear-cut (meaning a 95% harvest intensity) until reaching a certain quadratic diameter at breast height (DBH) limit. After reaching this limit, the probability of a clear-cut triples based on NFI observations. Besides clear-cuts, which are easily identified by their high removal intensity, other less intense harvesting practices were also classified as 'thinning' activities. In our approach, 'thinning' activities from the rule database were used not only for thinning within clear-cut regimes but also as the primary wood removal method for single-tree and group-tree selection systems, in order to reflect actual observed removal intensities. For the single-tree selection system, removals targeted larger diameter trees, whereas for the group-tree selection system, no diameter restrictions were applied.

In addition to harvesting practices, tree species selection was also incorporated into the Current and Biodiversity scenarios. If the management model predicted a species change in a

plot and the basal area of that plot fell below a specified threshold, a diversity feature was applied in the ingrowth setting of EFISCEN-Space. This took into account the dominant species on the plot, adding approximately 50 individuals of suitable species for the biogeographical region, which, according to the authors' interpretation, would promote diversification in the plot. For all scenarios, natural regeneration was considered following König et al. (2022). By combining the set of harvesting and the ingrowth rules it resulted in 40 combinations of rules that were used in the simulations.

We relied in the climatic projections of the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project, specifically the ISIMIP3b (Climate forcing dataset MPI-ESM1-2-HR) (Lange & Büchner, 2021). Altogether, we considered three management scenarios and 2 climate scenarios (see Section 3.1.2 for details), yielding six scenarios, as summarised in Table 3.2.

To assess the estimated impact on biodiversity and forest ecosystem services based on the result of the simulation of different scenarios in EFISCEN-Space, eight indicators were considered (Table 1.1). Regarding the biodiversity indicators, the share of uneven-aged forest structured follow the methodology proposed by Nabuurs et al., (2025), where the DBH dispersion of all trees in the plots was estimated using the Gini coefficient. According to the authors a stand can be consider uneven-aged when their Gini coefficient scores a value from 0.5 or above. The share of veteran trees per hectare refers to the proportion of tree which has a DBH of 40 cm or higher. The presence of tree microhabitats was estimated using the equations by Courbaud et al. (2022). During the calculation of the scale parameter for the Weibull function, the coefficient delta, representing site effect, was set to zero, as their values were not available.

3.1.2. Model initialisation data

EFISCEN-space was initialised for Baden Wuerttemberg and North Rhine-Westphalia based on the 3rd Bundeswaldinventur (Thünen-Institut, 2012). The measurements are taken from 4 sub-plots, which are 150 meters apart from each other, arranged in a square shape. In the initialisation each of these sub-plot was consider as an individual plot. As a result, around 12.700 valid plots were included in the simulations. A plot was considered invalid if it contained any missing data required for simulations.

3.2. Scenario results and interpretation

The results of all scenarios are presented in Figures 3.4-3.7. Overall, there are noticeable differences across the three management scenarios, but relatively small differences between climate scenarios. The largest differences between climate scenarios ranged from around 5 to 10% and are observed in the biodiversity indicators on the share of uneven-aged structure and share of veteran trees.

Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for Baden-Württemberg (SPP5-4.5)

Figure 3.2. Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for Baden-Württemberg (RCP4.5). The lines from a) to h) shows the mean of all simulated plots results.

Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for Baden-Württemberg (SPP5-8.5)

Figure 3.3. Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for Baden-Württemberg (RCP8.5). The lines from a) to h) shows the mean of all simulated plots results.

Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for North Rhine-Westphalia (SPP5-4.5)

Figure 3.4. Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for North Rhine-Westphalia (RCP4.5). The lines from a) to h) shows the mean of all simulated plots results.

Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for North Rhine-Westphalia (SPP5-8.5)

Figure 3.5. Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity indicators across simulated years for North Rhine-Westphalia (RCP8.5). The lines from a) to h) shows the mean of all simulated plots results.

According to our results, we identified significant differences for all indicators between the *Baseline* and *Current* scenarios. These results reflect differences between observed management practices as derived from repeated forest inventories and stated practices according to survey results. There can be several reasons for this difference. Firstly, differences in time frame considered could have affected these findings. The *Baseline* scenario is based on management actions derived from observations in the period 2002 and 2012, while the *Current* scenario represents the management that the forest owners stated in a survey conducted in 2023 and 2024. In recent years, German forests suffered from significant negative impact due to forest disturbances, especially wind through and bark beetle outbreaks (Viana-Soto & Senf, 2025). This could potentially impact on people’s management choices and which are not in our data and harvest rules based on observed harvest practices. Moreover, disturbances may require unplanned sanitary or salvage logging, but the harvest rules we used do not distinguish between unplanned and planned harvests. Secondly, many studies suggest that survey results may be affected by social desirability bias, i.e., respondents may present a more positive view of their own actions and behaviours to create a more socially desirable image (Gower et al., 2022; Graeff, 2005). Thirdly, the differences observed between the *Baseline* and *Current* results may simply reflect that the survey was not fully representative. More specifically, the survey may have involved respondents with more environmentally friendly behaviour. This is supported by our finding that 78% of the respondents stated they

conduct single-tree selection cutting in their forest (Maximo et al., 2025; Figure 3.2). Fourthly, respondents may not have fully understood the forest-related terminology used in the survey.

Overall, we observed similar results for the Current and Biodiversity scenarios, both of which are based on stated management, as indicated by the survey results. Our findings for these scenarios generally indicated an improvement in biodiversity indicators, except for the forest dominated by native tree species. This indicator measures the share of stands where the dominant species is considered native for Germany. The dominant species was identified as the species with the highest summed basal areas on the plot. Although most trees in the plots are native, this likely explains why, during the early years of the simulation, the Current and Biodiversity scenarios experienced a sudden decline in plots dominated by native trees. These scenarios used more group selection harvesting, which does not target specific diameters and therefore increases the likelihood of removing native trees compared to exotic ones. Conversely, the Baseline scenario did not exhibit such a sharp decline, likely because it employed more intensive harvesting methods, such as clear-cutting, primarily in plots dominated by exotic species. This indicates the importance of the type of harvests (and the species and tree size that are harvested), and not only the amount of harvesting.

For some indicators (tree species diversity and the share of veteran trees), differences between scenarios were time dependent. Tree species diversity was lowest in the Baseline scenario for most of the simulation period. Only by the end of the 2100 simulation period did tree species diversity in the Baseline scenario exceed that in the Current and Biodiversity scenarios. This result may be explained by larger harvest levels in the Baseline scenario, which stimulate regeneration and allow ingrowth by a larger set of tree species. The opposite effect was found for the share of veteran trees, which was generally highest in the Baseline scenario and decreased towards the end of the simulation period.

Apart from the indicators related to forest ecosystems and biodiversity, we observed significant differences in forest structures between the scenarios (Figure 3.8). Similar patterns appeared for both climate change scenarios, where the number of trees per hectare in the Baseline scenario is noticeably lower compared to the other scenarios. Likewise, the median diameter of the forests seems to decrease due to initially higher harvest levels. However, while the median decreases for the Baseline, it increases for the Biodiversity scenario and remains unchanged for the Current scenario. This may be explained by the reduction in clear-cutting activities between the two specified scenarios.

These differences in forest structure characteristics affect the performance of the different indicators. For example, according to Courbaud et al. (2022), the likelihood of some microhabitats (e.g., breeding-woodpecker-hole, rot-hole, or root-concavity) occurring in a tree increases with its diameter at breast height. Therefore, this group of tree microhabitats is more common in the *Current* and *Biodiversity* scenarios. Bark loss or dendrotelm are other tree microhabitats, but they are more common on smaller-diameter trees. It is important to note that stands with more trees have a higher probability of supporting tree microhabitats. However, the difference in this indicator's performance across the three scenarios is very small.

Figure 3.6. Forest structure across simulated years for both regions. The values shown in Tree per hectare graph represents the mean of all simulated plots results, while the second graph represents the median of DBH distribution.

The diameter distribution of the stands also appears to influence harvesting performance. In the initial years, harvesting in the Baseline scenario is relatively higher than in the other two; however, over time, they become more similar (Figures 3.4-3.7 and 3.9). Although stands in the Baseline scenario are generally more likely to undergo clear-cutting, the overall probability (averaged across species and biogeographical regions) of such events remains relatively low at approximately 6%. Since thinning, single-tree selection, and group selection follow the same management rules and differ only in their target DBH, the volume of wood removed seems similar. However, a significant difference can be observed in the number of trees harvested, which is notably higher in the Baseline and lower in the Current and Biodiversity scenarios. This difference is likely because the Current and Biodiversity management options typically target larger diameters compared to the Baseline scenario. Additionally, the reduction in diameter distribution over the years in the Baseline scenario means that more trees need to be harvested to meet the same harvest volume. This characteristic may influence the share of forest with an uneven-aged structure indicator, which performs better (approximately 10%) in the Baseline scenario. This is probably due to the higher harvesting intensity in the Baseline scenario, where harvesting more trees promotes stands with greater DBH diversity and facilitates regeneration, whereas low harvesting levels can lead to stagnation of the stand structure.

Figure 3.9. Average of trees harvested across all simulated plot over the years for both regions.

Regarding the share of veteran trees, the Baseline scenario has also performed better compared to the Current and Biodiversity scenarios. This could possibly be explained by the fact that, while the Baseline harvesting regime typically targets all DBH trees, the Current and Biodiversity targets mainly focus on larger DBH trees. The higher harvesting intensity in the Baseline scenario can also promote the development of remaining trees, helping median trees grow larger faster (i.e., veteran trees). By the end of the simulation years, it is apparent that the stated management scenarios reach or surpass the observed Baseline.

In Figure 3.107, the spatial distribution of the growing stock is shown. As shown in Figures 3.4-3.7, the growing stock is higher on the *Current* and *Biodiversity* scenarios, also it is possible to observe that over the different scenarios the same pixels seem to be following the same relative tendency. No distinct spatial trends can be identified at this resolution across the regions, although North-Rhine Westphalia presents greater variability in growing stock, whereas Baden-Württemberg seems more homogeneous.

Figure 3.10. Maps showing growing stock for RCP4.5 in the year 2100. The three panels show wood volume average by the plots included in the pixel size of $0.1^\circ.7$

3.3. Main findings

In this case study, we integrated forest owner typologies, socio-economic drivers, and management practices to estimate the future development of forest ecosystems in North-Rhine Westphalia and Baden-Württemberg. Forest owners and managers did not appear to make major changes in their management in our Biodiversity scenario compared to their current management in the Current scenario. This is likely because they already reported implementing biodiversity-friendly practices in their current management.

Overall, the results for our scenarios suggested potential future improvements in biodiversity, but the extent of these improvements depended on the specific scenario and timing considered. This indicates the importance of the type of harvest (and the species and tree size harvested), rather than the amount of harvesting alone. Moreover, we generally found a stronger effect of management on the indicators included in this case study than of climate.

Given the relatively significant differences observed between the Baseline (i.e., observed management from repeated forest inventory measurements) and Current (i.e., stated management in the survey) results on forest structure variables, it is important to investigate the underlying causes. Several explanations were proposed in this study; however, further research is needed to identify and address the issue properly.

4. Spain

4.1. Methods

4.1.1. Scenarios and implementation

In this case study, we used the FORMES multi-objective forest planning system to evaluate the results of the Biodiversity First policy scenario described in Chapter 2. We did not include the Multifunctionality and Wood Bioeconomy First scenarios because data on owner responses for these policy types were unavailable to parameterize them. The qualitative scenarios by Sotirov et al. (2025b; see section 2.2) have been updated based on the survey results (Sotirov et al. 2025a) concerning the key factors for forest owners when adopting different silvicultural practices (Maximo et al. 2025). The revised scenario description is available in Annex 1.

Table 4.1. Matching between drivers and their settings in the Biodiversity First policy scenario (Sotirov et al. 2025b) and socio-economic factors (Sotirov et al. 2025a).

Drivers	Driver setting	Socio-economic factors
Societal changes	Environmentally concerned stagnating society with reduced consumption	NA
Economic changes	Low traditional economic growth with low energy and low material (biomass) consumption	NA
Policy changes	Priority for nature conservation and climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level mainly governed by regulatory tools. partial support by subsidies	Subsidies for natural evolution Subsidies for forest management
Human and technological changes		Availability of labour Joint technical management and forest improvement plans Innovations that facilitate forest exploitation

For each agent typology, we explore whether each of socio-economic factors had an influence on the probability of changing forest management, represented in an additional question posed in the survey (Q8.2) – where we asked respondents their willingness to change their management practices to improve biodiversity in their forests following technical advice. There were no significant results based on the chi-square test or the Fisher test.

These results lead us to change the original plan on applying (Table 4.1. and (Sotirov et al. 2025b) where socio-economic factors related to the scenarios. Instead, new scenarios were defined only responding to survey (Q8.2), willingness to change their management practices to improve biodiversity in their forests following technical advice. Again, the results revealed that willingness to change is not strictly determined by typology. All four owner groups (i.e., environmentalists, traditionalists, optimizers, and multifunctionalists) include individuals open

to modifying their practices (see next section). As a result, the simulation was done for each forest inventory plot covered in the survey using the following implementation logic (Figure 4.1.)

Figure 4.1. Forest management scenarios and implementation

SCENARIO BAU includes all the respondents of the survey. This scenario assumes that their management follows the silvicultural prescriptions are based on the Guidelines for Sustainable Forest Management in Catalonia (ORGEST) developed for the main tree species present in the region¹. The ORGEST series constitute a set of technical tools to help forest management planning. They collect a series of decision elements, models and management recommendations, adjusted to Catalan conditions, which constitute a body of practical and up-to-date information on forest management, as described by Maximo et al. (2025) and their Table 16. They aim to support the manager in the decision-making process regarding the allocation of preferential objectives and the planning and execution of management actions.

SCENARIO C2N includes the respondents that indicated the willingness to adopt Closer to nature practices (52.05%) and the rest, which continue with BAU. For this 52.05% a new prescription (BIO-ORGEST) to adopt close-to-nature principles was applied (Beltrán et al. 2020, Baiges et al. 2023). These BIO-ORGEST are widely accepted by technicians and researchers, as described by Maximo et al. (2025) and their Table 17. From the management decisions, we implemented changes in the harvesting methods to link a specific agent (regardless of its type) to a change in prescription in their associated inventory plot.

SCENARIO NOMAN represents a no-management scenario. Here, we hypothesize that all forests in Catalonia were left to natural evolution. This last scenario is relevant for at least three reasons: i) to contrast the indicators from the previous scenarios to a no-management option; ii) natural evolution as an alternative to active-management approaches existing in conservation policies and advocated for re-wilding; iii) forest and land abandonment as one of the challenges in Catalonia. Currently, only a 30% of forests account with a formal forest management plan². In this case, the simulations no not contemplate any management prescriptions.

For all scenarios, forest dynamics were simulated from 2021 to 2050 (3 decades) for the climatic scenarios Representative Concentration Pathways 4.5 and 8.5. We relied in the

¹ https://cpf.gencat.cat/es/cpf_actualitat/cpf_publicacions/cpf_colleccions/cpf_orientacions_gestio_forestal_sostenible/

² <https://www.observatoriforestal.cat/planificacio-forestal/Idescat 2023>

climatic projections of the global circulation model MPI-ESM-LR downscaled with the RCA4 regional model for Spain. We had access to daily climatic projections for the meteorological stations of the Meteorological Service of Catalonia, that were originally obtained from the CORDEX program of COPERNICUS (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-projections>). We applied a spatial interpolation approach to obtain the future series of climate variables required by FORMES, based on climate data from COPERNICUS, the topographic variables from PNOA, and using the methods included in the R-package meteoland (De Cáceres et al. 2018).

4.1.2. Agent typology and willingness to change.

Table 4.2 shows, by agent typology, the willingness to adjust practices such as thinning, species selection, regeneration, or specific biodiversity measures. For instance, 51% of environmentalists and 45% of optimizers reported a willingness to change their harvesting methods. Biodiversity measures also receive strong support, particularly among environmentalists and traditionalists. These results underscore that, despite their different profiles, all typologies are inclined to reconsider certain aspects of their management, especially those related to ecological resilience and stand-level improvements. This overall openness provides a solid foundation for extension services to promote closer-to-nature management practices.

Table 4.2. Percentage of respondents for each agent typology willing to change their management to improve biodiversity.

Agent typology	Change in cutting method	Change in thinning	Change in species selection	Change in regeneration	Change in biodiversity
TRAD	48.2	62.5	50.1	48.2	57.1
OPTI	45.8	70.8	54.2	56.2	43.8
MULTI	43.6	62.8	52.1	53.2	51.1
ENVI	51.0	69.4	57.1	59.2	55.1

We also check if there was a significant relation between the change of cutting method and any of the socio-economic factors we asked about in the survey. Figure 4.2 shows the plots for this analysis and we can see how those forest owners with a non-inherited property, lower studies, members of a forest owners' association and younger want to change their cutting method than the other respondents. Although these small differences, there were not significant based on chi square test or fisher test.

Figure 4.2. Characterization of the willingness to change depending on respondents' socio-economic factors

4.1.3. Model initialisation data

We aimed at simulating forest evolution for each owner answering the survey under a climate change scenario and according to different alternative management scenarios. To simulate forest dynamics adopting different management rationalities. we used the FORMES projection system for multi-objective forest planning (see D3.1). FORMES is based on a series of empirical, climate-sensitive, individual-tree models to simulate forest stands dynamics (Trasobares et al. 2022). The forest inputs of the FORMES models are NFI-like data. That is, a set of forest stands or plots for each of them describing their composition and structure via four variables: tree species, diameter at the breast height (cm), height (m), and density (trees/ha). Additional plot-level data required by the FORMES model are topography (elevation (m), slope ($^{\circ}$), and aspect ($^{\circ}$)), area in hectares (optional parameter), climatic variables (mean annual temperature ($^{\circ}$ C), annual precipitation (mm), potential evapotranspiration (mm), and solar radiation (MJ/m^2)). and soil water holding capacity (mm). We initialized as follows each of these plot- and stand-level data.

Using the publicly available coordinates of the Spanish NFI plots, we extracted the three topographic variables required from the Digital Terrain Model at 25 m of spatial resolution (DTM25). The DTM25 has been obtained by interpolating 5-m resolution digital terrain models derived from the interpolation of the terrain class from PNOA LiDAR flights (<https://pnoa.ign.es/web/portal/pnoa-lidar/modelo-digital-del-terreno>). Topographical variables are used by FORMES model as explanatory variables in the individual-tree models of growth, mortality, and ingrowth.

Finally, the soil water holding capacity was described based on soil physical properties. such as texture (i.e., volume percent of sand, silt and clay), organic matter content, bulk density and rock fragment content corresponding to plot coordinates obtained from the SoilGrids global database at 250 m resolution (Hengl et al. 2017).

4.1.4. Agent allocation

To initialize the forest data for each owner with complete survey responses (234), we assigned one or more plots from the 4th Spanish National Forest Inventory (sampled between 2016 and 2017 in Catalonia) based on the ownership location (either the municipality or, if not available, the county), the property right type (public or private), whether it has a protection status, whether the forest is considered mono-species or multi-species, and the main tree species (up to three). This process resulted in 1107 NFI plots used to describe the current composition and structure of the forest stands analyzed. Examining the distribution of dominant species at the ownership level (Figure 4.1), we observe that pine species are the most common (as dominant species). They range from 40% of the OPTI ownerships to 62% of the ENVI. Overall, *Quercus* species are the second most common dominant species, especially notable among optimizers, with 49% of these forests dominated by *Quercus*, compared to 40% by pine. Minor species or genera in Mediterranean forests, such as birch, Douglas fir, or balsam fir, are not even present as dominant species in the forests of optimizers. Forests belonging to multifunctionalists are the most diverse, represented by up to seven different genera or 13 dominant species (Figure 4.3).

Management is simulated in FORMES based on tree-specific silvicultural prescriptions that are applied according to rules dictating when thinning occurs, what type of thinning is used, how much wood is removed, and the minimum DBH for final cuts during regular management. More details on how management is implemented in FORMES are provided by Maximo et al. (2025).

Figure 4.3. Distribution of the dominant species of the forest ownerships when classified in the four typologies considered: environmentalists (ENVI), multifunctional (MULTI), optimizers (OPTI), and traditionalists (TRAD).

4.2. Scenario results and interpretation

The results of the C2N scenario are represented in Figure 4.4. We distinguish between forest owner typologies in different colours associated to a municipality. For those municipalities for which we had more than one observation, we use the majority of the forest owners' typology, and the same criteria were used to select if the municipality area had forest owners who wanted to change. This respondents' willingness to change management to improve the biodiversity in their forest is represented by diagonal lines. We observe that the respondents from the biggest municipalities are more willing to change their management method for a close to nature one. We only plot the municipalities for those we have, at least, on respondent and the rest are represented in grey colour.

Forest Owner Typologies by Municipality
 Diagonal lines mark majority willing to change harvest method

Figure 4.4. Map of Catalonia forests owner's typology and its willingness to change the management method to improve biodiversity.

Figure 4.5. Map of Catalonia with private forests without forest management plan (as proxy of passive forest owners)

Figure 4.5. shows the amount of private forest plots without forest management plan. Passive owners are the fifth category in the FOT typology (Sotirov et al. 2025a) – which represents owners detached from their properties and forest management. We assume that the survey did not reach this type, therefore figure 4.5. could be considered as a proxy for the passive owners' location in Catalonia. Comparing both maps, we can see that many of the grey area in Figure 4.4. overlaps with the potential location of passive forest owners (Figure 5.5.).

Indicators and its interpretation

Through 2021-2100, the three management scenarios differed in their annual growth volume patterns, mirroring the differences in annual harvest volume for the two scenarios with active management (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). All the management scenarios showed similar values and steadily increasing patterns in terms of carbon storage and growing stock (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). For the RCP 4.5 climate scenario, and under the BAU scenario where all owners continue with business-as-usual management, the carbon stock reached 242.2 Mg C/ha by 2100, representing an increase of 148.1 Mg C/ha compared to 2020 (Table 4.3). At the same time, the annual growth volume decreased from 3.0 to 0.66 m³/ha/yr, while wood removals remained between 0.28 and 0.112 m³/ha/yr during the simulation period (Figure 4.6). In contrast, the NOMAN scenario led to the highest increase in carbon stock (+156.7 Mg C/ha, +166.3% compared to 2020) as well as in growing stock (+157.7 m³/ha, +101.7% compared to 2020), but it completely eliminated timber supply, highlighting a trade-off between carbon sequestration and wood production. Significantly, it is the reduction in annual growth volume of 2.24 m³/ha/yr in 80 years by the NOMAN scenario, meaning that the exclusion of silvicultural treatments slowed down stand productivity and growth, as competition between trees increases. Finally, the BAU-C2N scenario, in which roughly half of the owners shift towards close-to-nature management, provided the largest wood removals levels (between 0.28 and 0.27 m³/ha/yr; Figure 4.4). For this scenario, the annual growth volume is the highest among the scenarios, and it's maintained close to 1 m³/ha/yr by the end of the century (Figure 4.6), while carbon stocks reached 246.6 Mg C/ha and a growing stock of 305.3 m³/ha (Table 4.3). Overall, these results suggested that close-to-nature management can offer an effective compromise by achieving very high carbon sequestration, maintaining the growing stock (instead of decreasing the growing capacity of the forests), while still allowing for a sustainable level of timber harvest, whereas the exclusive reliance on either intensive management or complete abandonment limits the balance between these three indicators. Under the RCP 8.5 climatic scenario, the trends for growth volume, carbon stock, and wood removals are similar to the RCP 4.5, but the growing capacity of the trees is slightly lower (Figure 4.6).

In terms of biodiversity-related indicators describing forest structure and composition, the three scenarios show contrasting outcomes by 2100 for some of these indicators (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). Dead wood exhibits a similar increasing trend across all management scenarios, with the lowest absolute volume in the BAU scenario and no difference between climate scenarios (Tables 4.3 and 4.4). Over the 80-year period, forest stand composition is more likely to vary from one time period to the next when applying silvicultural treatments involving thinning and/or final cuts if these treatments also involve planting new species after final cuts. However, in our simulations all the regeneration is natural. As a result, the variation in species composition following management is very low indicators (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). At the same time, there is significant variability in forest composition among the analysed plots, which may obscure local effects of silvicultural interventions on tree species diversification. Additionally, there is little to no distinct impact of the two climate projections on these indicators. For example, under RCP 8.5, the BAU scenario shows a slight decrease in tree species diversity to 0.68 (−1.7% compared to 2020), and the mean area share of the dominant species in all stands rises to 72.2% (Table 4.4). Conversely, the NOMAN and BAU-C2N scenarios display greater species and structural diversity throughout the simulation period, suggesting that unmanaged forests tend to develop greater structural heterogeneity over time. Overall, these results indicate that close-to-nature management not only enhances species diversity more than either business-as-usual or non-management but also promotes structural complexity. This offers a pathway to balance biodiversity objectives with other forest functions.

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Figure 4.6. Indicator development for net annual increment, total carbon stock, growing stock, annual harvested volume, annual dead volume, area share of the dominant species, area share of mixed forest (those with any species basal area > 70%), coefficient of variation in DBH, Shannon index, and growing stock during the period 2020 – 2100 for the three forest management scenarios and the RCP 4.5 climate scenario.

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Figure 4.7. Indicator development for net annual increment, total carbon stock, growing stock, annual harvested volume, annual dead volume, area share of the dominant species, area share of mixed forest (those with any species basal area > 70%), coefficient of variation in DBH, Shannon index, and growing stock during the period 2020 – 2100 for the three forest management scenarios and the RCP 8.5 climate scenario.

Table 4.3. Summary of the results at long-term (2100) for the three forest management scenarios and the RCP 4.5 climate scenario. Absolute and relative differences are with respect to the initial value in 2020 of the corresponding variable.

Scenarios	BAU			NOMAN			BAU-C2N		
	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ
Annual growth volume (m ³ /ha/yr)	0.66	-2.22	-77.1	0.65	-2.24	-77.6	0.95	-2.16	-69.4
Carbon stock (t/ha)	242.2	148.1	157.3	250.7	156.6	166.3	246.6	152.4	161.9
Growing stock (m ³ /ha)	299.3	144.3	93.0	312.7	157.7	101.7	305.3	150.2	96.9
Wood removals (m ³ /ha/yr)	0.12	-0.16	-55.7	-	-	-	0.27	-0.12	-30.0
Dead volume (m ³ /ha/yr)	1.89	1.28	211.0	2.01	1.40	228.7	1.89	1.28	211.1
Area share of dominant species (%)	72.1	0.31	0.4	71.4	-0.41	-0.6	71.8	-0.05	-0.1
Area share of mixed forests (%)	46.2	0.85	1.9	45.7	0.43	0.9	49.1	3.85	8.5
Shannon index (-)	0.68	-0.01	-1.6	0.69	-0.002	-0.3	0.68	-0.005	-0.8
Coefficient variation of DBH (-)	0.42	0.02	4.2	0.47	0.07	17.6	0.43	0.03	8.7

Table 4.4. Summary of the results at long-term (2100) for the three forest management scenarios and the RCP 8.5 climate scenario. Absolute and relative differences are with respect to the initial value in 2020 of the corresponding variable.

Scenarios	ALL_BAU			ALL_NOMAN			BAU_C2N		
	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ	2100	abs.Δ	%Δ
Annual growth volume (m ³ /ha/yr)	0.56	-2.38	-81.1	0.33	-2.86	-89.6	0.54	-2.78	-83.6
Carbon stock (t/ha)	232.0	137.8	146.4	239.2	145.1	154.1	235.5	141.3	150.1
Growing stock (m ³ /ha)	286.0	130.9	84.5	298.9	143.9	92.8	293.0	137.9	89.0
Wood removals (m ³ /ha/yr)	0.22	-0.06	-22.6	-	-	-	0.17	-0.22	-56.5
Dead volume (m ³ /ha/yr)	1.78	1.16	186.5	1.92	1.30	210.4	1.86	1.25	204.9
Area share of dominant species (%)	72.0	0.19	0.3	71.1	-0.73	-1.0	71.9	0.06	0.1
Area share of mixed forests (%)	46.6	1.28	2.8	45.3	0	0	48.7	3.42	7.5
Shannon index (-)	0.68	-0.01	-1.7	0.69	0	0	0.68	-0.01	-1.3
Coefficient variation of DBH (-)	0.42	0.02	3.9	0.47	0.07	3.9	0.44	0.04	9.6

4.3. Main findings

The analysis highlights how forest owner typologies, socio-economic drivers, and management scenarios collectively shape the future of forest ecosystems. Owners show varying levels of willingness to modify their practices: while traditional (TRAD) and multifunctional (MULTI) owners are moderately open to changes in cutting, thinning, and regeneration methods, environmentally oriented (ENVI) owners exhibit the strongest readiness to adopt biodiversity-

friendly practices. This is followed closely by optimizers (OPTI) owners, especially in thinning and regeneration. These behavioural patterns are influenced by key drivers such as infrastructure and transport, profitability of forest management, and forest-specific factors like age structure, productivity, and natural disturbance risks.

Looking ahead to 2100, the scenario analysis reveals important trade-offs. Business-as-usual management (BAU) cannot sustain initial levels of wood removals and shows a lower increase in carbon stocks. Annual growth patterns are negative over the 80-year periods regardless of the climatic scenario analysed, resulting in less diversity in both forest structure and tree community composition. By contrast, no-management (NOMAN) maximizes carbon stocks and growing stock, and enhances uneven-aged structures, though it provides no timber output and its annual growth volume is systematically lower than in managed scenarios. The mixed approach, BAU-C2N, where close-to-nature practices coexist with conventional management, achieves the best balance: carbon stock increases beyond business-as-usual, growing stock shows the best trends compared to the other two management approaches, species diversity reaches levels similar to the NOMAN scenario, and structural heterogeneity is promoted—all while increasing wood supply.

It is important to note that within an 80-year period (between 2020 and 2100), it is already possible to observe major changes in forest indicators, such as changes in forest composition or structure, since processes like species diversification, regeneration, and structural transformation unfold slowly over time. However, the management strategies applied do not explicitly target creating new mixtures, planting new species or combinations of them. The steady increase of carbon and growing stocks has to be read with caution, as the performed simulations do not include natural disturbances (such as fires or pest outbreaks) that could largely modify the stocks of living biomass, even more in a climate change context that entails increasing risk and impact of disturbances.

Overall, the findings suggest that encouraging greater adoption of close-to-nature management (especially among owners already inclined toward environmental or optimization goals) could improve biodiversity and carbon storage without fully sacrificing economic returns. This offers a promising way for sustainable forest management.

5. Sweden

5.1. Methods

5.1.1. Scenarios and implementation

In Sweden, the leading national forest management decision support system Heureka (Lämås et al. 2023) was used to simulate and evaluate the expected short- and long-term consequences of forest owners' behavioral adaptations to three different policy scenarios. First, a reference scenario (referred to as BAU) was derived, simulating the ongoing forestry in the current study area and applying the climate scenario RCP4.5 (as in the three alternative policy scenarios). Other climate scenarios, like RCP8.5, are available in Heureka. However, applying these climate scenarios comes with a disclaimer since the downsides with a warmer climate, mainly comprehensive forest damages like fires and floodings (currently followed by landslides), are not modelled or available for simulation in Heureka. Common for all simulated scenarios are also:

- The use of a discount rate of 2%.
- A time horizon of 100 years represented by 20 5-year periods where forest management activities (harvest operations etc.) are simulated in the middle of each 5-year period.
- The use of a model optimizing the net present value with respect to even-flow constraints limiting the total harvest volumes not to vary with more than 15% from one 5-year period to the next 5-year period.

The BAU scenario was compared with three alternative policy scenarios (Chapter 2):

- Scenario 1: Biodiversity first.
- Scenario 2: Multifunctionality.
- Scenario 3: Wood bioeconomy first.

As described in Sotirov et al. (2025b), the EU-level scenarios were adapted to fit the Swedish context. Initially, a survey was distributed to forest owners and managers in Norrbotten County. Based on the survey results, three agent types were identified in the county: Optimizers, Multifunctionalists, and Environmentalists (Maximo et al. 2025). The data on agent types was combined with survey data on owner categories (state and other public owners; corporations and church owners; non-industrial private owners) enabling an assessment of the relative prevalence of each agent type within each forest owner category. The adapted scenarios were then presented to forest-owners in a series of local workshops, each workshop targeting owners of a specific agent type. Before the workshops, the forest owners responded to selected questions in the above-mentioned survey and based on their responses they could be divided into distinct agent types – and corresponding workshop groups. In the workshops, each group of owners, representing one agent type, described how they would change their management relative to the BAU scenario. When simulating the scenarios in Heureka, this information was used to inform the regional-level survey results so that distinct forest management responses could be constructed for each owner category in ways that reflected the behaviour of the three forest owner types included in the category:

- State and other public owners.
- Corporations and church owners.
- Non-industrial private forest owners.

The somewhat weak correlations between these forest owner categories and three agent typologies (Optimizers, Multi-functionalists, and Environmentalists) are discussed by Maximo et al. (2025). As described above, any behavioural adaptations were investigated by questionnaires and group discussions held at workshops with representatives of the forest owner categories before the simulations. Forest management prescriptions for each scenario was developed based on the distribution of each agent typology within each owner category, as described in Table 6.1 by Maximo et al. (2025). Agent type behaviours are thus considered and incorporated into the responses of each owner category. The Table shows the aggregated impacts of the responses of all owner categories. The different adaptations for each forest owner category and policy scenario were then translated into specific settings in Heureka PlanWise to simulate a particular scenario, as described in Tables 5.1-5.3.

Table 5.1. Simulated forest management in scenario 1: Biodiversity first. The primary management adaptations (see “adapted even-aged forestry” in the table below), relative to the current even-aged rotation management informing the reference (or BAU) scenario (see above), include prolonged rotation periods, promoting of broadleaves, extensive extraction of wood and no extraction of harvest residuals. The management changes and adaptations described below are based on the forest owner’s responses to the conditions stipulated in the scenario description.

Forest domain*	Area (ha)	Share	Forest management
Protected areas (wildlife preserves etc.)	549340	14.1%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (volunteer pres.)	183245	4.7%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (set aside patches)	272936	7.0%	Free development/Unmanaged
Biodiversity and/or societal high value areas	269508	6.9%	Continuous cover forestry and enhanced preservations (30% set aside)
Contorta forests	88988	2.3%	Contorta liquidation. followed by adapted even-aged forestry
Public forests, old growth etc.	364955	9.4%	Free development/Unmanaged
Public forests with broadleaves etc.	475849	12.2%	Broadleaf promoting continuous cover forestry and general preservations (15% set aside)
Public forests	311541	8.0%	Adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (15% set aside)
Corporate forests, old growth etc.	128362	3.3%	Free development/Unmanaged
Corporate forests	222450	5.7%	Adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (15% set aside)
Private, small-scale forests	1029452	26.4%	Adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (15% set aside)
<i>Sum:</i>	3896626	100.0 %	

*) Subareas, with specific characteristics, of the analysis area (described in section 5.1.2).

Table 5.2. Simulated forest management in scenario 2: Multifunctionality.

Forest domain*	Area (ha)	Share	Forest management
Protected areas (wildlife preserves etc.)	549340	14.1%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (volunteer preserves)	183245	4.7%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (set aside patches)	272936	7.0%	Free development/Unmanaged
Biodiversity and/or societal high value areas	269508	6.9%	Continuous cover forestry and enhanced preservations (30% set aside)
Public forests, old growth etc.	337095	8.7%	Free development/Unmanaged

Public forests, spruce dominated etc.	78693	2.0%	Adapted even-aged forestry with fertilization (according to Sveaskog) and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Public forests, areas suitable for exotic tree species	81265	2.1%	Adapted even-aged forestry with exotic tree species (according to Sveaskog) and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Public forests, lichens and low productive areas	159153	4.1%	Reindeer herding-adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Public forests, middle-aged areas	185591	4.8%	Continuous cover forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Public forests	347331	8.9%	Productivity-adapted even-aged forestry (according to Sveaskog) and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Corporate forests, lichens and low productive areas	84923	2.2%	Reindeer herding-adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Corporate forests, high productive areas	207602	5.3%	Productivity-adapted even-aged forestry (according to the corporations) and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Corporate forests	96361	2.5%	Even-aged forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Private, small-scale forests, pine dominated and low productive areas	206701	5.3%	Adapted even-aged forestry with exotic tree species and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Private, small-scale forests, spruce and broadleaf dominated areas	208139	5.3%	Adapted even-aged forestry with fertilization and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Private, small-scale forests	628744	16.1%	Even-aged forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
<i>Sum:</i>	389662 6	100.0 %	

*) Subareas, with specific characteristics, of the analysis area (described in section 5.1.2).

Table 5.3. Simulated forest management in scenario 3: Wood and bioeconomy first. Here, the adaptations of the even-aged forestry imply production enhancements, shortened rotation periods, promoting of conifers and intensive extraction of wood and harvest residuals.

Forest domain*	Area (ha)	Share	Forest management
Protected areas (wildlife preserves etc.)	549340	14.1%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (volunteer preserves)	183245	4.7%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (set aside patches)	272936	7.0%	Free development/Unmanaged
Biodiversity and/or societal high value areas	269508	6.9%	Continuous cover forestry and enhanced preservations (30% set aside)
Public forests, spruce dominated etc.	103047	2.6%	Adapted even-aged forestry with intensive fertilization and general preservations (5% set aside)
Public forests, areas suitable for exotic tree species	129752	3.3%	Adapted even-aged forestry with exotic tree species and general preservations (5% set aside)
Public forests	956328	24.5%	Adapted even-aged forestry (according to Sveaskog) and general preservations (5% set aside)
Corporate forests, spruce dominated etc.	44186	1.1%	Adapted even-aged forestry with intensive fertilization and general preservations (5% set aside)
Corporate forests, areas suitable for exotic tree species	58152	1.5%	Adapted even-aged forestry with exotic tree species and general preservations (5% set aside)

Corporate forests	286547	7.4%	Adapted even-aged forestry (according to the corporations) and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
Private, small-scale forests	1043584	26.8%	Adapted even-aged forestry and general preservations (7.5% set aside)
<i>Sum:</i>	3896626	100.0%	

*) Subareas, with specific characteristics, of the analysis area (described in section 5.1.2).

5.1.2. Model initialisation data

The initial state of the forest in the current analysis area, the county of Norrbotten with 3,896,626 hectares of productive forest land, was described using data from the National Forest Inventory (Fridman et al. 2014) and its 3470 sample plots surveyed in the area during 2016-2020. Norrbotten is the northernmost county in Sweden, with latitudes between 65 and 69° N, where the pine-dominated forest (57% of standing stock), 25% spruce, and the remaining share mostly birch are described in Table 5.4 and Figure 5.1.

Table 5.4. Characteristics of the initial state of the forest in the analysis area (3 896 626 ha).

Average standing stock (m ³ /ha)	95.8
Average stand age (yrs)	80.1
Average wood productivity potential (m ³ /ha, yr)	2.9

Figure 5.1. Age class distribution of the initial state of the forest in the analysis area (3 896 626 ha).

Note that old forests, which consist of 679,735 hectares (17.4%) of forests with a basal area-weighted stand age over 135 years, are largely either formally protected or designated as informal set-asides to be left unmanaged; both in reality and in the simulations. The area distribution in all four scenario analyses, when simulating different forest management regimes, can be seen in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5. Initial subarea distribution of the analysis area (3 896 626 ha).

	Area (ha)	Share	Forest management
Protected areas (wildlife preserves etc.)	549340	14.1%	Free development/Unmanaged
Informally protected areas (volunteer preserves)	183245	4.7%	Free development/Unmanaged

Informally protected areas (set aside patches)	272936	7.0%	Free development/Unmanaged
Biodiversity and/or societal high value areas	269508	6.9%	Continuous cover forestry and enhanced preservations (30% set aside)
Other, managed areas	2621596	67.3%	Forestry adapted to each forest owner group and policy scenario, respectively
<i>Sum:</i>	3896626	100.0%	

Note that in the simulations of forest management tailored to the behaviour of the three forest owner groups across the three alternative policy scenarios, the differentiation was made for the 2,621,596 hectares of managed forest land. The distribution of the area in the three policy scenario analyses concerning the three forest owner groups can be seen in Table 5.6.

Table 5.6. Forest owner distribution of the managed part of the analysis area (2 621 596 ha).

Forest owner group	Area (ha)	Share
State and other public	1189127	45.4%
Corporations and church	388885	14.8%
Non-industrial private (small scale)	1043584	39.8%
<i>Sum:</i>	2621596	100.0%

In Heureka, the effects of global warming on forest growth and similar factors are simulated using a model by Freeman (2009). The climate change scenario corresponding to RCP4.5 was used in all scenario analyses.

5.2. Scenario results and interpretation

The results from the simulations of the three alternative scenarios are summarized in Tables 5.7-5.9. Note that year 0, or period 0, is a “starting point” from which the simulations begin. Heureka simulates the development of the forest in five-year steps, considering the forestry activities (like harvest operations) during these periods. This means that period 1 covers years 1-5, period 2 covers years 6-10, and so on, up to period 20, which corresponds to years 96-100. When estimating by period, this approach is valid for years 1-5, 6-10, and so forth. This contrasts with point estimates, which are valid for years 2.5, 7.5, and so on—that is, the middle of each period. Additionally, all simulations start at year 0. Year 2.5, which falls in the middle of the first five-year period, is the first “stop” point when looking into the future with Heureka. All forestry activities are simulated at the midpoint of each five-year period. Correspondingly, all point estimates are valid immediately before the simulation of any forestry activity at the midpoint of each period.

The results, usually average values over the entire 100-year time horizon but sometimes average values for the first ten (or 20) years for each scenario, are compared to the corresponding results for the BAU scenario. Important forest and ecosystem service indicators, along with biodiversity indicators, are highlighted. Overall, the presented results can be interpreted as describing the forest management simulated in each scenario.

Table 5.7. Simulation results from scenario 1: Biodiversity first, compared to results from the reference scenario (BAU), for the analysis area of Norrbottens county (3 896 626 ha).

Indicator variable* (unit)	BAU	Scenario 1	Rel. Difference
Average harvest/extracted roundwood (m ³ /ha, yr):	1.54	1.20	-22.2%
Average standing/growing stock (m ³ /ha):	152	175	15.6%
Average standing/growing stock of broadleaves (m ³ /ha):	21.5	27.2	26.8%
Average current annual increment, net (m ³ /ha, yr):	2.88	2.90	0.6%
Average tree biomass carbon stock (ton C/ha):	58.1	66.7	15.0%
Average tree biomass carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.35	0.48	37.0%
Average soil carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.03	0.05	46.8%
Average soil carbon flux year 1-20 (ton C/ha, yr):	-0.09	-0.11	-22.5%
Average share of old broadleaf forests:	8.7%	12.1%	38.9%
Average deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.22	66.8%
Average total deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.22	66.8%
Average amount of veteran trees (m ³ /ha):	16.8	21.1	25.4%
Average amount of species rich forests (ha):	375484	502683	33.9%

*) For the 100-year planning horizon, if nothing else stated.

Table 5.8. Simulation results from scenario 2: Multifunctionality, compared to results from the reference scenario (BAU), for the analysis area of Norrbottens county (3 896 626 ha).

Indicator variable* (unit)	BAU	Scenario 2	Rel. Difference
Average harvest/extracted roundwood (m ³ sub/ha, yr):	1.54	1.55	1.0%
Average standing/growing stock (m ³ /ha):	152	159	4.7%
Average standing/growing stock of broadleaves (m ³ /ha):	21.5	21.2	-1.5%
Average current annual increment, net (m ³ /ha, yr):	2.88	3.03	4.9%
Average tree biomass carbon stock (ton C/ha):	58.1	60.4	4.1%
Average tree biomass carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.35	0.40	14.5%
Average soil carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.03	0.05	36.8%
Average soil carbon flux year 1-20 (ton C/ha, yr):	-0.09	-0.09	-1.9%
Average share of old broadleaf forests:	8.7%	8.7%	-0.1%
Average deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.15	14.0%
Average total deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.15	14.0%
Average amount of veteran trees (m ³ /ha):	16.8	17.7	5.3%
Average amount of species rich forests (ha):	375484	401508	6.9%

*) For the 100-year planning horizon, if nothing else stated.

Table 5.9. Simulation results from scenario 3: Wood Bioeconomy first, compared to results from the reference scenario (BAU), for the analysis area of Norrbottens county (3 896 626 ha).

Indicator variable* (unit)	BAU	Scenario 3	Rel. Difference
Average harvest/extracted roundwood (m ³ sub/ha, yr):	1.54	1.75	13.5%
Average standing/growing stock (m ³ /ha):	152	147	-3.3%
Average standing/growing stock of broadleaves (m ³ /ha):	21.5	19.3	-10.2%
Average current annual increment, net (m ³ /ha, yr):	2.88	3.09	7.1%
Average tree biomass carbon stock (ton C/ha):	58.1	56.1	-3.3%
Average tree biomass carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.35	0.34	-2.4%
Average soil carbon flux (ton C/ha, yr):	0.03	0.04	23.8%
Average soil carbon flux year 1-20 (ton C/ha, yr):	-0.09	-0.08	-8.0%
Average share of old broadleaf forests:	8.7%	8.2%	-6.0%
Average deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.12	-12.4%
Average total deadwood formation (m ³ /ha, yr):	0.13	0.12	-12.4%
Average amount of veteran trees (m ³ /ha):	16.8	14.2	-15.7%
Average amount of species rich forests (ha):	375484	347432	-7.5%

*) For the 100-year planning horizon, if nothing else stated.

Examples of period-specific results from the policy scenario analyses are shown in Figures 5.2 to 5.7. In some cases, for certain indicator variables, significant differences only appear after a relatively long time, in the second half of the 100-year planning horizon. However, in other cases, rapid changes are visible, such as for the carbon flux, which relates to climate change mitigation. A key finding from the scenario analyses is that forest owner behaviour matters, sometimes in the short term and other times in the long term.

Overall, the differences between the various scenarios are minor. This appears true even if forest owners or managers anticipate significant behavioural changes in the different policy scenarios. Therefore, more than path dependencies, the results are likely influenced by limited flexibility due to relatively intensive management of the forest landscape over several decades.

Figure 5.2. Average standing stock, in cubic meters per hectare, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Figure 5.3. Average standing stock of broadleaves, in cubic meters per hectare, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Figure 5.4. Average harvest, in cubic meters per hectare and year, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Figure 5.5. Average growth, in cubic meters per hectare and year, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Figure 5.6. Average carbon stock, in tonnes per hectare, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Figure 5.7. Average carbon flux, in tonnes per hectare and year, for policy scenario 1: Biodiversity first, 2: Multifunctionality and 3: Wood and bioeconomy first, respectively, during a planning horizon of 100 years for Norrbotten.

Across the three scenarios, the Biodiversity-First strategy produced the most significant deviations from business-as-usual, creating major benefits for biodiversity and carbon-related metrics but causing notable trade-offs in timber production and economic returns. The biggest positive changes include sharp increases in rotation length (+84%) and deadwood formation (+67%), along with substantial gains in soil and total carbon flux (+37–47%), species-rich forest area (+34%), and veteran tree abundance (+25–26%). These improvements come at the cost of sharp declines in harvest outputs (–20 to –25%), net revenue (–18%), and net present value (–22%), indicating a system strongly shifted toward structural complexity and long-term carbon storage rather than wood production. In contrast, the Multifunctionality scenario shows moderate positive benefits across most ecosystem services, with small to medium gains in biodiversity (e.g., deadwood +14%) and carbon flux (+16–37%), coupled with slight improvements in timber yield and economic indicators (around +1%), while avoiding major trade-offs. The Bioeconomy-First scenario prioritizes timber production and revenue, demonstrating the largest increases in harvested stemwood and roundwood (+13–14%), net revenue (+7%), and total carbon flux (+24% for soil carbon flux; +3–23% in other carbon variables), but at the expense of declines in most biodiversity indicators—including veteran trees (–13 to –16%), species-rich forests (–8%), and deadwood (–5%)—reflecting a focus on wood provisioning over ecological complexity.

Overall, these results highlight strong synergies between biodiversity conservation and carbon storage, moderate compatibility among ecosystem services under multifunctionality, and clear trade-offs between bioeconomic objectives and biodiversity-related ecosystem services. Importantly, caution should be exercised when interpreting these results due to limitations in Heureka’s ability to project outcomes for non-standard forestry practices in Sweden (e.g., selective logging), as well as its inclusion of only positive (growth increases) but not negative (disturbance increases) impacts of human-driven climate change in the projections.

5.3. Main findings

Across the three policy pathways, the Biodiversity-First strategy causes the greatest shift from current practices by increasing habitat indicators and carbon storage while significantly reducing timber outputs and economic returns. The Multifunctionality approach achieves more balanced results, providing moderate improvements in both habitat for biodiversity and carbon metrics, along with slight gains in timber production and revenue, with few notable trade-offs. The Bioeconomy-First strategy, on the other hand, focuses on wood supply and financial performance, raising harvest levels and revenues but leading to declines in multiple biodiversity indicators. Overall, the results show that biodiversity and carbon storage goals

tend to support each other, multifunctional management offers broad compatibility among services, and bioeconomic intensification involves clear ecological costs.

6. European Union

6.1. Methods

The Global Forest Model (G4M) is a spatially explicit biophysical forest model developed and maintained by IIASA to simulate forest development under various management and climate scenarios on national, continental, and global scales (Kindermann et al. 2013). The model operates on a spatial grid, where each pixel represents biophysical properties for even-aged stands of different ages across multiple species and species types. Forest growth parameters are derived from empirical yield tables, local climate, and surface properties. For this project, we have created a new description of European forests calibrated with publicly available datasets, added a dynamic model for standing deadwood, lying deadwood, and litter that considers the effects of litterfall, mortality, harvests, disturbances, and decomposition, using the Yasso20 model (Viskari et al. 2022). We have also coupled this with the wildFire cLimate impacts and Adaptation Model (FLAM; Krasovskii et al. 2018) to simulate wildfire occurrence and severity based on fuel availability from our litter and deadwood model, climate data, and suppression efficiency. All these models are calibrated to European datasets covering the historical period from 1990 to 2020.

6.1.1 Scenarios and implementation

For this study, forest management after the historical period is modeled in G4M using the management approach described in Section 6 of Maximo et al. (2025), with the management decisions summarized in their Table 25. All forests are assumed to be managed by one of the four agent types identified from survey responses, as explained in Maximo et al. (2025). These types are multifunctionalists, optimizers, environmentalists, and traditionalists (see Sotirov et al. 2025a for descriptions). Separate management models for each agent type were developed for three scenarios: current management, management aimed at improving biodiversity, and management for climate adaptation. We refer to these scenarios as *current*, *bio*, and *clim*, respectively. These scenarios vary based on the management decisions for five options discussed below (thinning/harvest, species selection, regeneration method, biodiversity enhancement, and post-disturbance management), which are informed by survey responses. The current scenario reflects responses about existing management, the bio scenario relates to management for biodiversity restoration and conservation, and the clim scenario pertains to management for climate change adaptation. For each set of responses, a random forest method was used to spatialize management decisions across Europe. This approach required estimates of the area coverage for each agent type, based on reported survey data. Here, we primarily focus on the current and bio scenarios.

Management decisions directly impact both the living and DOM components of the model, which then indirectly affect the fire model. Table 25 of Maximo et al. (2025) shows how survey responses were converted into management options in G4M.

- **Thinning and harvesting regimes:** This determines whether thinning and/or final harvest are performed in the pixel. In G4M, this is represented as binary choices between thinning and no thinning, and between cutting and no cutting, which directly influence the stock development and age structure in the living forest model, as well as the removals and the rate at which species composition changes over time. This also directly impacts the DOM model, especially since harvest residuals contribute to the total amount of litter and lying deadwood.
- **Species selection for regeneration:** This determines which species (i.e., broadleaf or needleleaf) are replanted after forested areas are cleared due to harvests, natural mortality, and disturbances. This is important for both growth productivity and the

dynamics of the relative proportions of broadleaf and needleleaf forests at each location. The broadleaf versus needleleaf fraction directly affects litter dynamics, as litter from different forest types has different decomposition rates.

- **Regeneration method:** This determines whether a growth productivity multiplier is applied to all forests within the pixel, which directly affects living stock development and litterfall rates.
- **Biodiversity improvement method:** Depending on the decision, the forest can be set aside as unmanaged, meaning regeneration always occurs with the same species and no productivity multiplier, primarily affecting the development of the living stock. In a managed forest, it can also influence the amount of harvested wood that remains in the forest as residuals, altering the dynamics of the lying deadwood.
- **Post-disturbance management:** This determines whether deadwood stays in the forest or is removed by salvage logging, affecting the dynamics of both standing and lying deadwood.

The only change in the management model compared to the model in Maximo et al. (2025) is that we do not use the biodiversity improvement method question to determine if harvesting occurs within a pixel. This is because, in some models, this question led to unrealistically large areas with no harvest due to the decision to leave forest untouched without active management, even though the biodiversity improvement management scenario predicted that harvesting would happen within the pixel.

Time-dependent precipitation, mean temperature, solar radiation, and wind speed for our forest growth, litter and deadwood decomposition, and FLAM models are extracted from the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 dataset (Thrasher et al., 2022). Climate projections were taken for two scenarios: SSP2-4.5 (a “middle-of-the-road” socioeconomic pathway, approximately corresponding to RCP4.5 in CMIP5), and SSP5-8.5 (a fossil-fuel-intensive pathway, roughly matching RCP8.5). Corresponding CO₂ concentration pathways for these scenarios were obtained from Meinshausen et al. (2020), and population densities used in the FLAM fire suppression model were sourced from CIESIN (2017).

We calculated the development of the living component of the forest for both climate scenarios and each management scenario. Models are run for each agent type separately, assuming all forested areas are covered by that agent type. The individual agent models are then combined using the methodology described in Section 6.3 of Maximo et al. (2025). This is done by dividing the geographic area into four separate regions: Europe-North, Europe-East, Europe-South, and Europe-West. Within each region, the fractional area covered by each agent type is determined from the total forested areas provided in the survey responses.

6.1.2 Model initialisation data

For this case study, we constructed and calibrated a new description of European forests using G4M on a Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area grid with each pixel covering a 10km x 10km area. The species categories considered are evergreen needleleaf, evergreen broadleaf, deciduous needleleaf, and deciduous broadleaf. The forested areas within each pixel in 2020 are determined from the forest map given by Avitabile et al. (2024) and the distribution of this area among the four species categories in and prior to 2020 is determined by the MODIS land cover product (Friedl & Sulla-Menashe 2022). Changes in the total forested area in between 1990 and 2020 were derived from data given in the State of Europe’s Forests 2020 report (Forest Europe, 2020), with an approximately linear 9% increase being observed during this time. After 2020, no afforestation, reforestation, and deforestation is assumed to take place meaning the forested area in each pixel is assumed to be constant. A map of total forest area in our model

is shown in Figure 6.1. The fraction forested areas in IUCN protected area categories I-III were derived from the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA; UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2025 May release).

Figure 6.1 Forested area given as the fraction of each 10km x 10km pixel covered by forest (left panel), above ground biomass within the forested regions of each pixel (middle panel), and gross annual increment in each region (right panel) derived from the maps given by Avitabile et al. (2024). These are used as the forest map and the primary constraint on forest properties in 2020.

We constrain the forest above-ground biomass on a pixel-by-pixel basis and the gross annual increment on a subnational regional grid using the dataset of Avitabile et al. (2024). These datasets are shown in Figure 6.1. The forested area and biomass maps imply a total stock of 7.3×10^9 tC in 2020. The development of forest stock on a country by country basis during the calibration period is obtained from the FAO Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020 (FAO, 2020), which we use to initialize the total European stock in 1990. Total roundwood removals were obtained for each year and for each country from the FAOSTAT Forestry domain (FAO, 2025). The total stock during the calibration period in our calibrated model is compared to these statistics in Figure 6.2.

Figure 6.2 Total European forest stock of stemwood carbon during the calibration period from our model compared with FRA stock statistics for the years 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2015, and from Avitabile et al. (2024) for 2020.

For calibrating the litterfall and deadwood models, we rely on official national statistics for total litter and deadwood stocks during the calibration period, obtained from the FAO Global Forest Resource Assessment 2020 (FAO, 2020). The FLAM model was calibrated and validated using historical burned area data from the European Space Agency’s (ESA) MODIS FireCCI51 product (Chuvieco et al. 2018, 2019). Table 6.1 summarizes all input datasets used in our models.

Table 6.1: Data used to initialize, calibrate, and run G4M and FLAM.

Variable	Type	Usage	Source
Forest 2020 area	Spatial map	Set area mask in years >2020	Avitabile et al. (2024)
Forest 2020 biomass	Spatial map	Biomass distribution in year 2020 for model calibration	Avitabile et al. (2024)
Forest 2020 increment	Regional statistics	Calibration of forest growth in 2020	Avitabile et al. (2024)
Species fractional cover	Spatial maps	Species distributions <2020	Friedl & Sulla-Menashe (2022)
Forest country stocks (1990-2020)	Country statistics	Growth model calibration and validation	FAO (2020)
Total forest removals (1990 to 2020)	Country statistics	Constrain final harvest amount	FAOSTAT (2025)
Total area (1990 to 2020)	Total statistics on European scale	Constrain afforestation and reforestation in calibration period	Forest Europe (2020)
Forest protected area	Spatial map	Mask out unmanaged forests in strictly protected areas	UNEP-WCMC & IUCN (2025)
Litter stocks	Country statistics	Constraints on litterfall	FAO (2020)
Deadwood stocks	European statistics	Calibration of deadwood models	FAOSTAT (2025)
Burned areas (2000 to 2020)	Spatial/temporal maps	Calibration and validation of FLAM	Chuvieco et al. (2018; 2019)
Population density	Spatial/temporal maps	FLAM fire suppression model	CIESIN (2017)
Precipitation	Spatial/temporal maps	Productivity and FLAM models	Thrasher et al. (2022)
Temperature	Spatial/temporal maps	Productivity and FLAM models	Thrasher et al. (2022)
Solar radiation	Spatial/temporal maps	Productivity model	Thrasher et al. (2022)
Near surface relative humidity	Spatial/temporal maps	FLAM model	Thrasher et al. (2022)
Wind gust	Spatial/temporal maps	FLAM model	Thrasher et al. (2022)

6.2. Scenario results and interpretation

6.1.1 Living forest

The development of total stocks in Europe for both climate scenarios and each management scenario are shown in Figure 6.3. The total stock is defined as the total mass of stemwood carbon in all European forests. In all scenarios, the total stock increases by the end of the

century, which is primarily due to forest aging, especially since the total forested area is held constant after 2020. This is consistent with the rapid growth between 1990 and 2020, which was approximately a 50% increase in total stock during this time period. However, we expect that the growth seen in this time period has slowed due to a decrease in the increment, potentially due to age effects (Vangi et al., 2024) or drought related productivity changes (Hertzog et al., 2025), which we likely do not fully capture in our model, meaning that the total growth seen by the end of the century is potentially overestimated. The higher climate scenario shows a more rapid growth in forest stock in the first half of the century followed by slower growth after 2060 and an overall lower total stock by 2100, though both climate scenarios are similar.

Figure 6.3 Total European stemwood carbon stock change from 2020 for both climate scenarios considered (SSP245 and SSP585) and for the three management scenarios, as described in Section 6.1.1.

All management scenarios lead to very similar developments of the total European stocks, with the current scenario having a marginally higher stock by the end of the century to the other two scenarios (Figure 6.4). The differences in total stock between the management scenarios is mostly due to the main regeneration method which applies an increase in growth productivity when regeneration is done with material obtained from tree breeding or enrichment planting. This is more common in the current scenarios, whereas our management model predicts that regeneration using regular planting material and natural regeneration are more regular in the bio scenarios. In Figure 6.5, we show a pixel-by-pixel comparison between biomass in the current and bio management scenarios broken down by pixels where the productivity increase is applied in the current scenario only, the bio scenario only, both scenarios, and neither scenario separately, demonstrating the importance of this decision. This is also the most important management decision for determining the litter stocks as shown below.

Figure 6.4 Stemwood carbon density and its projected changes. Upper row: Maps showing stemwood carbon densities for SSP245 in the year 2050. The three panels show biomass density for the current management scenarios (left panel), and the differences between the two other scenarios and the current scenario (middle and right panels). Note that in these panels, in order to make the distribution most visible, the colour scheme does not show the entire range of values. Lower row: Forest area weighted histograms of the ratio of biomass density in the bio management scenario to biomass density in the current management scenario for the years 2050 and 2100.

Figure 6.5 Stemwood carbon density in the living forest in the bio management scenario against the value in the current management scenario broken down by pixels where the productivity increase happens in the current scenario only (red), the bio scenario only (blue), both scenarios (green), and neither scenarios (grey). This is for the SSP245 climate scenario and the multifunctionalist management type. This shows that the main regeneration method management decision is primarily responsible for differences in stock between the management scenarios.

The differences between individual agents within a scenario are also small, as shown for the SSP245 climate and current management scenario in Figure 6.6, which displays the development of average biomass density and total cumulative removals broken down by agent type. One possible reason why the total stock development is similar across all scenarios is that the main factors affecting stock development are harvest and thinning intensity, which were not examined in the survey used for our management model. As a result, we only observe shifts between the binary options of harvest/no-harvest and thinning/no-thinning. Since our management model reasonably predicts that harvest and thinning almost always occur, this results in similar total stocks in all cases. Any changes in rotation time or harvest amounts that might occur due to different management objectives are not represented in our model.

Figure 6.6 Development of living stemwood carbon density for the SSP245 climate scenario and the current management scenario broken down by agent types (left panel) and cumulative average removals for each case (right panel). The removals include harvests, thinning activities, and disturbances.

Although the total European stock is similar across different scenarios and agents, larger variations become evident when examining the spatial distribution of stock. Figure X illustrates the distributions of the differences between management scenarios and the histograms of the ratio of biomass density in the bio management scenario compared to the current management scenario. Some regions show higher stock in the current scenario than in the bio scenario, while others are lower, with differences reaching up to 20% in either direction.

In Figure 6.7, we show the development of the percentage of forested area covered by broadleaf and needleleaf forests for each climate and management scenario considered, along with the breakdown of these percentages by agent type. In all cases, there is a general trend toward more broadleaf forest. The bio management scenario results in the highest broadleaf fraction, while the current management scenario results in the lowest. This trend varies significantly between the agent types. For the optimizers, the broadleaf fraction by the end of the century is much higher under the bio management scenario than under the current scenario.

Spatial distributions of these changes in the current and bio cases are examined in Figure 6.8. While the overall trend leans toward more broadleaf forest, significant areas of western Europe, especially in France, show a trend toward increased needleleaf forest. The shift toward broadleaf forest is most prominent in northern Europe, although in Scandinavia, the largest changes are only observed in the bio case. The notable shift in the far north is partly due to

the low initial broadleaf share. In Alpine regions, despite the high needleleaf fraction at the start of the models, the broadleaf fraction can either increase or decrease, with no clear trend. However, it is important to note that the group of respondents our management model is based on does not include anyone responsible for managing Alpine forests, meaning the management decisions are entirely derived from extrapolations and interpolations from other regions.

6.1.2 Deadwood, litter and burned area

In Figure 6.7, we show the fractional changes in the total European carbon stocks of litter, standing, and lying deadwood between 2020 and 2100 for all three management scenarios and both climate scenarios. In all cases, we observe a strong decrease in litter stock during this period due to rising temperatures causing more rapid decomposition. This is evident from the lower litter stocks found in the more extreme climate scenario. The management scenario has a much smaller impact on litter stocks compared to climate change effects. The current scenario has a slightly higher stock than the other two, which is related to the management decision on the main regeneration method. This method involves increasing growth productivity when regeneration uses material obtained from tree breeding or enrichment planting, which is more common in the current scenario. Higher growth productivity leads to increased litterfall and, consequently, a higher litter stock.

Figure 6.7 Development of total carbon stocks in European forests in the litter (upper-left panel), the lying deadwood (upper-right panel), and in the standing deadwood (lower-left panel) components for the three management scenarios and both climate scenarios considered.

In our model, the litterfall rate at any location depends on that year's increment, not the amount of biomass present. Therefore, an increase in stock does not necessarily lead to higher inputs into the litter pool. For deadwood, inputs are residuals from natural mortality, disturbances, and harvests. The input rate of deadwood then depends on the total forest biomass; thus, any management decisions affecting the stock indirectly influence the amount of deadwood present. Some parts of the management model directly influence deadwood levels and are both significant. The decision regarding disturbance residuals is crucial because mortality caused by disturbances from insects and diseases is the largest source of standing deadwood and disturbance residuals from windthrow is an important source of lying deadwood. Whether these residuals are removed or left in the forest impacts the local amount of standing deadwood. Additionally, the main diversity improvement method allows some pixels to add an extra 10% of harvest residuals to lying deadwood. One of the key management decisions that directly affects deadwood is whether to perform thinning. If thinning occurs in a pixel, residuals are added to the lying deadwood pool. If not, increased natural mortality adds more carbon to the standing deadwood pool.

Since we assume no decomposition of standing deadwood, the climate-related effects only indirectly influence the carbon stocks. This results in a relatively small difference between climate scenarios and a larger impact of management decisions. Our models show that on local scales, the choice to remove disturbance residuals or not is significant. Pixels have notably lower amounts of standing deadwood if disturbance residuals are removed. On a European scale, this management decision affects both the current and bio management scenarios equally, but in different locations, and therefore does not change the overall differences in the total European stock of standing deadwood shown in Figure 6.7. The

difference in the total Europe-wide stocks between these scenarios is primarily due to the decision of whether to perform thinning.

Figure 6.8 Upper row: Spatial distributions of standing and lying deadwood in 2050 for the current management scenario and SSP245. Middle row: Change in standing deadwood between 2020 and 2050 for the current (left) and bio (middle) management scenarios, and the difference between the two scenarios (right) for SSP245. Lower row: The same as the middle row but for lying deadwood.

For lying deadwood, climate driven changes in the decomposition rates have a much larger effect on total carbon stocks. In our models, the dominant source of lying deadwood is harvest (including thinning) residuals. The management scenario also has an effect similar to that of

the standing deadwood described above. While the decisions to leave or remove disturbance residuals and to whether to perform thinning influence the local amount of lying deadwood, the total European stocks are the same in the current and bio management scenarios.

The 2050 spatial distributions of standing and lying deadwood in the current management model for SSP245, along with comparisons of the changes in both of these quantities between 2020 and 2050 for the current and bio management scenarios, are shown in Figure 6.8. The largest increases in both components are typically observed in Norway, Sweden, and Finland, although lying deadwood decreases in much of southern Sweden and Finland. The differences between these scenarios on a pixel-by-pixel basis are shown more clearly in Figure 6.9, showing that locally standing deadwood varies substantially more than lying deadwood between the two scenarios.

Figure 6.9 Pixel by pixel comparison of deadwood amounts in the bio and current management scenarios separated for standing lying deadwood.

In Figure 6.10, we present the total integrated burned areas calculated with our litter and deadwood data and the FLAM model. We show both annual burned area and cumulative burned area for each management and climate scenario. Cumulative burned area is useful because the stochastic nature of annual burned areas makes comparing different scenarios difficult. The management decisions from our model only affect the fuel stock in forested areas of each pixel, primarily consisting of litter and lying deadwood. Since these two components are similar across different management scenarios, we observe only a small effect of management on the total burned area. The impact of the climate scenario is much more significant because the more extreme climate conditions provide a better environment for fire ignition and spread.

Figure 6.10 Yearly (upper panel) and cumulative (lower panel) burned area for each management and climate scenario calculated using the litter and deadwood estimates from Section 6.2.2 and FLAM.

6.3. Main findings

The modeling results for this case study provide European-wide predictions of how forest structure, carbon dynamics, and disturbance risks change under different forest management strategies and climate scenarios throughout the 21st century. Overall, the simulations show a continued increase in total carbon stocks across Europe, mainly driven by forest growth, moderate increases in the share of broadleaf species, decreases in litter stocks, increases in deadwood stocks, and a rise in the expected burned area from wildfires.

Differences between management scenarios (current, biodiversity-focused ‘bio’, and climate-adaptation ‘clim’) are relatively small at the scale of the entire European stock. This is likely influenced by the survey-derived management model (Maximo et al., 2025), which only includes binary decisions about whether to harvest or not and whether to thin or not. Both decisions are chosen to be implemented almost everywhere in each scenario. Management choices that forest managers are more likely to change and that could significantly impact carbon stocks, such as harvest or thinning intensities, were not included in the survey or the management model. Future surveys designed to inform forest models should explicitly

examine variations in harvest and thinning intensities, as these factors are crucial for determining long-term carbon dynamics in large-scale forest models like G4M.

The main factor in our management model that creates differences in carbon stocks is the regeneration method. When managers keep harvest intensity the same but aim for biodiversity-friendly replanting, the total carbon stock in Europe increases less than with current management practices. This is because the choice of regeneration method in biodiversity-friendly replanting often favours techniques like planting with regular planting material and natural regeneration over more productive methods, such as using material from tree breeding. If this biodiversity-friendly replanting was part of a broader biodiversity improvement management strategy that also involved reducing harvest intensity, we would expect higher carbon stocks in Europe in the bio management scenario. These results suggest that the carbon-sequestration benefits of biodiversity-oriented management may be more limited than expected unless combined with adjustments in harvest intensity.

The results indicate that forest managers tend to stick with existing practices even when faced with different objectives and that any changes they are likely to implement will not significantly alter the fundamental properties of forests across Europe. Policy-driven incentives will be crucial to encourage shifts in forest management so managers are motivated to adopt new practices. Future research combining surveys of forest managers with large-scale forest models could also help frame potential management changes in terms of incentives for making beneficial decisions. A proactive range of management strategies might include introducing non-native or highly productive tree species, speeding up the transition from coniferous to broadleaved forests, and designating set-aside conservation areas, among other options.

On local scales within Europe, management effects are more apparent. Comparisons of individual pixels reveal localized differences of up to $\pm 20\%$ in living forest biomass between scenarios. While all scenarios show a general shift toward more broadleaf cover, the bio scenario accelerates this trend most strongly, with significant increases in northern Europe and more modest or even opposite trends in western Europe, where needleleaf may expand under some management-climate combinations. Agent-type differences are also notable: multifunctionalists and optimizers display the largest shift toward broadleaf forests, with the latter also showing the greatest divergence in broadleaf expansion between the current and bio scenarios.

For deadwood and litter, climate has a stronger influence than management. Rising temperatures accelerate decomposition, leading to significant declines in litter stocks, especially under the SSP585 climate scenario, while management has a smaller impact, mainly driven by differences in growth productivity. Note that changes in total stock are less relevant for litter stocks. We expect that harvest intensity would be important if included in our models since it affects forest age and, consequently, growth rates. Standing deadwood responds more strongly to management, particularly through thinning decisions and whether deadwood caused by disturbance-induced mortality is removed (salvage logging). The absence of thinning results in higher natural mortality and, therefore, more standing deadwood, although these effects vary across locations. Lying deadwood is most influenced by changes in decomposition and harvest residuals, with climate parameters and management both playing significant roles.

Despite these structural changes, wildfire outcomes show only limited sensitivity to management. Because fuel loads are mainly influenced by litter, which is mostly determined by forest growth productivity and climate factors, the burned area remains nearly unchanged across management scenarios. The climate scenario is influential with two opposing effects: higher temperatures create conditions that favour fires but also speed up decomposition,

reducing fuel availability. Overall, we find that more extreme climate scenarios lead to an increase in the total area affected by fire. However, our model does not account for changes in fire suppression efficiency.

The geographic distribution of survey respondents also limits our ability to interpret the management model. Responses were collected from northern Sweden, parts of Germany, Poland, Slovenia, and Catalonia, leaving large areas of Europe, such as the Alpine region, unrepresented. As a result, the spatial patterns of management decisions predicted by our model and the forest properties that result from these decisions are, in much of Europe, based on extrapolations of management behaviour into areas where we lack direct information. Future work of this type could benefit from a more comprehensive geographic distribution of survey respondents when it is practically feasible.

7. Synthesis

This study aimed to examine how behaviour and behavioural change can support improvements in forest biodiversity and promote more sustainable socio-ecological forest systems, including synergies and trade-offs. We evaluated the results of selected policy and management scenarios using forest simulation models that were recently expanded to incorporate human behaviour and behavioural change. We conducted these assessments for three regional case studies in Germany, Spain, and Sweden, as well as an EU-level case study. Across all four case studies, we found that changes in forest management behaviour can enhance biodiversity, but the extent of improvement depends heavily on the magnitude of management change and the practices modified.

Additionally, we observed that biodiversity-friendly management practices are positively associated with carbon storage in forests, particularly when management (particularly harvest) intensity is reduced. In the German case studies, the biodiversity scenario resulted in the largest carbon accumulation in forests, regardless of the climate scenarios considered. In the Swedish case study, the biodiversity-first and multifunctional scenarios simultaneously improved habitat indicators and forest carbon stocks. Similarly, in the Spanish case study, the no-management and close-to-nature scenarios enhanced carbon stocks, structural heterogeneity, and species diversity. At the European level, all scenarios show increasing total carbon stocks over time, and biodiversity-oriented regeneration methods contribute to structural changes such as increased broadleaf cover and deadwood accumulation.

Our results also emphasize the importance of the type and intensity of management practices. The German case study showed that biodiversity outcomes are affected by what is harvested (tree species, size, and harvest type) not just by the quantity harvested. This aligns with the findings from the Spanish and Swedish case studies, where close-to-nature or multifunctional approaches can provide balanced outcomes for biodiversity, carbon, and timber supply. In Sweden, biodiversity-first management clearly reduced timber supply and revenues, while multifunctional management minimized these trade-offs. In the Spanish case study, the no-management scenario maximized biodiversity and carbon storage but eliminated timber production, whereas closer-to-nature management served as a compromise that still increased wood supply.

Across the four cases, management effects often had a greater influence than climate effects on biodiversity-related and other indicators included in our study, especially forest structure, forest carbon, and deadwood. In the German and Spanish case studies, management had a stronger impact than climate on most indicators examined. In the EU case study, several indicators (e.g., standing deadwood) were more strongly affected by management decisions (e.g., thinning and salvage logging) than by climate, but, for example, litter stocks mainly were affected by climate. These findings suggest that behavioural changes among forest owners and managers can significantly influence biodiversity outcomes even amid climate change.

All case studies highlight behavioural inertia as a key limiting factor for significant changes in forest structure and composition, as well as biodiversity indicators. Policy-driven incentives can help encourage shifts in forest management, but forest managers and owners often indicated or exhibited limited deviations from current practices in favour of forest biodiversity. Results from the German case studies suggested that many owners already perceive themselves as applying biodiversity-friendly practices. Future research combining surveys of forest managers with large-scale forest models could also help frame potential management changes in terms of incentives for making beneficial decisions.

References

- Avitabile, V., Pilli, R., Migliavacca, M., Duveiller, G., Camia, A., Blujdea, V., Adolt, R., Alberdi, I., Barreiro, S., Bender, S., Borota, D., Bosela, M., Bouriaud, O., Breidenbach, J., Cañellas, I., Čavlović, J., Colin, A., Di Cosmo, L., Donis, J., Fischer, C., Freudenschuss, A., Fridman, J., Gasparini, P., Gschwantner, T., Hernández, L., Korhonen, K., Kulbokas, G., Kvist, V., Latte, N., Lazdins, A., Lejeune, P., Makovskis, K., Marin, G., Maslo, J., Michorczyk, A., Mionskowski, M., Morneau, F., Myszowski, M., Nagy, K., Nilsson, M., Nord-Larsen, T., Pantic, D., Perin, J., Redmond, J., Rizzo, M., Šebeň, V., Skudnik, M., Snorrason, A., Sroga, R., Stoyanov, T., Svensson, A., Talarczyk, A., Teeuwen, S., Thürig, E., Uva, J., Mubareka, S., (2024). Harmonised statistics and maps of forest biomass and increment in Europe. *Scientific Data* 11, 274. [10.1038/s41597-023-02868-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02868-8)
- Beland Lindahl, K., Sténs, A., Sandström, C., Johansson, J., Lidskog, R., Ranius, T., Roberge, J.-M., (2017). The Swedish forestry model: More of everything? *Forest Policy and Economics* 77, 44-55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2015.10.012>
- Center For International Earth Science Information Network-CIESIN-Columbia University. (2017). *Gridded Population of the World, Version 4 (GPWv4): Population Density, Revision 11 (Version 4.11)* [Data set]. Palisades, NY: NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC). <https://doi.org/10.7927/H49C6VHW> Date Accessed: 2025-12-18
- Chuvieco, E., Lizundia-Loiola, J., Pettinari, M.L., Ramo, R., Padilla, M., Tansey, K., Mouillot, F., Laurent, P., Storm, T., Heil, A., Plummer, S., (2018). Generation and analysis of a new global burned area product based on MODIS 250 m reflectance bands and thermal anomalies. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 10, 2015-2031. [10.5194/essd-10-2015-2018](https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-2015-2018)
- Chuvieco, E., Pettinari, M. L., Lizundia Loiola, J., Storm, T., Padilla Parellada, M. (2019), ESA Fire Climate Change Initiative (Fire_cci): MODIS Fire_cci Burned Area Grid product, version 5.1, <https://doi.org/10.5285/3628cb2fdb443588155e15dee8e5352>.
- Courbaud, B., Larrieu, L., Kozak, D., Kraus, D., Lachat, T., Ladet, S., Müller, J., Paillet, Y., Sagheb-Talebi, K., Schuck, A., Stillhard, J., Svoboda, M., Zudin, S., (2022). Factors influencing the rate of formation of tree-related microhabitats and implications for biodiversity conservation and forest management. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 59, 492-503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14068>
- De Caceres, M., Martin-StPaul, N., Turco, M., Cabon, A., Granda, V. (2018). Estimating daily meteorological data and downscaling climate models over landscapes. *Environmental Modelling and Software*. 108. 186-196.
- Deuffic, P., Sotirov, M., Arts, B., (2018). “Your policy, my rationale”. How individual and structural drivers influence European forest owners’ decisions. *Land Use Policy* 79, 1024-1038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.09.021>
- FAO (2020). *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020 – Main report*. Rome. FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9825en>
- FAO (2025). *FAOSTAT: Forestry domain*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Rome. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FO> (accessed 5 March 2025).
- Feliciano, D., Franzini, F., Schelhaas, M.J., Haltia, E., Bacciu, V., Boonen, S., Filipek, S., Häyriinen, L., Lindner, M., Menini, A., Nieberg, M., Ofoegbu, C., Peltoniemi, M., Stancioiu, T., Staritsky, I., Uzquiano, S., Wiersma, H. (2025). Decision rules, parameters, and narratives for modelling. ForestPaths project deliverable D1.3.
- Filipek S., et al. (in preparation), Rule patterns of European forest management based on repeated National Forest Inventory tree measurements.
- FOREST EUROPE (2020). *State of Europe’s Forests 2020*.
- Fridman J., Holm S., Nilsson M., Nilsson P., Ringvall A. H. & Ståhl G. 2014. Adapting National Forest Inventories to changing requirements – the case of the Swedish National Forest Inventory at the turn of the 20th century. *Silva Fennica* 48: 3 article id 1095.
- Friedl, M., Sulla-Menashe, D., (2022). MODIS/Terra+Aqua Land Cover Type Yearly L3 Global 500m SIN Grid V061 [Data set]. NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center. <https://doi.org/10.5067/MODIS/MCD12Q1.061> Date Accessed: 2025-08-28
- Gower, T., Pham, J., Jouriles, E. N., Rosenfield, D., & Bowen, H. J. (2022). Cognitive biases in perceptions of posttraumatic growth: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 94, 102159.

- Graeff, T. R. (2005). Response bias. In K. Kempf-Leonard (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Social Measurement* (pp. 411-418). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-12-369398-5/00037-2>
- Groeneveld, J., Müller, B., Buchmann, C.M., Dressler, G., Guo, C., Hase, N., Hoffmann, F., John, F., Klassert, C., Lauf, T., Liebelt, V., Nolzen, H., Pannicke, N., Schulze, J., Weise, H., Schwarz, N., (2017). Theoretical foundations of human decision-making in agent-based land use models – A review. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 87, 39-48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2016.10.008>
- Haase, M., et al. (in prep.). How to achieve diverse EU forest policy objectives? Stakeholder preferences on policy implementation using land sparing or sharing approaches under different future scenarios.
- Hengl, T., Mendes de Jesus, J., Heuvelink, G.B.M., Ruiperez Gonzalez, M., Kilibarda, M., Blagotić, A., Shangguan, W., Wright, M.N., Geng, X., Bauer-Marschallinger, B., Guevara, M.A., Vargas, R., MacMillan, R.A., Batjes, N.H., Leenaars, J.G.B., Ribeiro, E., Wheeler, I., Mantel, S., Kempen, B., (2017). SoilGrids250m: Global gridded soil information based on machine learning. *PLOS ONE* 12, e0169748. [10.1371/journal.pone.0169748](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169748)
- Hertzog, L., Piedallu, C., Lebourgeois F., Bouriaud, O., & Bontemps, J.-D. (2025), Turning point in the productivity of western European forests associated with a climate change footprint, *Science of the Total Environment*, 967, 178843, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178843>
- Kindermann, G., Schorghuber, S., Linkosalo, T., Sanchez, A., Rammer, W., Seidl, R., Lexer, M., (2013). Potential stocks and increments of woody biomass in the European Union under different management and climate scenarios. *Carbon Balance and Management* 8, 2. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1750-0680-8-2>
- Krasovskii, A., Khabarov, N., Pirker, J., Kraxner, F., Yowargana, P., Schepaschenko, D., & Obersteiner, M. (2018). Modeling Burned Areas in Indonesia: The FLAM Approach. *Forests*, 9(7), 437. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f9070437>
- König, L.A., Mohren, F., Schelhaas, M.-J., Astigarraga, J., Cienciala, E., Flury, R., Fridman, J., Govaere, L., Lehtonen, A., Muelbert, A.E., Pugh, T.A.M., Rohner, B., Ruiz-Benito, P., Suvanto, S., Talarczyk, A., Zavala, M.A., Vega, J.M., Staritsky, I., Hengeveld, G., Nabuurs, G.-J., (2025). Combining national forest inventories reveals distinct role of climate on tree recruitment in European forests. *Ecological Modelling* 505, 111112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2025.111112>
- Lämås, T., Sängstuvall, L., Öhman, K., Lundström, J., Årevall, J., Holmström, H., Nilsson, L., Nordström, E.-M., Wikberg, P.-E., Wikström, P., Eggers, J., (2023). The multi-faceted Swedish Heureka forest decision support system: context, functionality, design, and 10 years experiences of its use. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change Volume 6 - 2023*. [10.3389/ffgc.2023.1163105](https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2023.1163105)
- Lange, S., & Büchner, M. (2021). ISIMIP3b bias-adjusted atmospheric climate input data (v1.1). <https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.842396.1>
- Leclère, D., Obersteiner, M., Barrett, M., Butchart, S.H.M., Chaudhary, A., De Palma, A., DeClerck, F.A.J., Di Marco, M., Doelman, J.C., Dürauer, M., Freeman, R., Harfoot, M., Hasegawa, T., Hellweg, S., Hilbers, J.P., Hill, S.L.L., Humpenöder, F., Jennings, N., Krisztin, T., Mace, G.M., Ohashi, H., Popp, A., Purvis, A., Schipper, A.M., Tabeau, A., Valin, H., van Meijl, H., van Zeist, W.-J., Visconti, P., Alkemade, R., Almond, R., Bunting, G., Burgess, N.D., Cornell, S.E., Di Fulvio, F., Ferrier, S., Fritz, S., Fujimori, S., Grooten, M., Harwood, T., Havlík, P., Herrero, M., Hoskins, A.J., Jung, M., Kram, T., Lotze-Campen, H., Matsui, T., Meyer, C., Nel, D., Newbold, T., Schmidt-Traub, G., Stehfest, E., Strassburg, B.B.N., van Vuuren, D.P., Ware, C., Watson, J.E.M., Wu, W., Young, L., (2020). Bending the curve of terrestrial biodiversity needs an integrated strategy. *Nature* 585, 551-556. [10.1038/s41586-020-2705-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2705-y)
- Maximo, Y.I., Hasegawa, M., Nabau, J., Pecurul, M., Aquilué, N., Kraxner, F., Johnstone, C.P., Shchepaschenko, D., Krasovskiy, A., Kindermann, G., Park, E., House, J., Nordström, E.-M., Pezdevšek Malovrh, Š., Verkerk, P.J., (2025). Report on Improved Forest models with enhanced representation of behavior and behavioral change of forest owners and conservation managers. BIOCONSENT Project deliverable report 3.1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14801478>
- Meinshausen, M., Nicholls, Z.R.J., Lewis, J., Gidden, M.J., Vogel, E., Freund, M., Beyerle, U., Gessner, C., Nauels, A., Bauer, N., Canadell, J.G., Daniel, J.S., John, A., Krummel, P.B., Luderer, G., Meinshausen, N., Montzka, S.A., Rayner, P.J., Reimann, S., Smith, S.J., van den Berg, M., Velders, G.J.M., Vollmer, M.K., Wang, R.H.J., (2020). The shared socio-economic pathway (SSP) greenhouse gas concentrations and their extensions to 2500. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 13, 3571-3605. [10.5194/gmd-13-3571-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-3571-2020)
- Nabuurs, G.J. et al. (in prep). Contemporary high-resolution European forest structure assessed using tree-level National Forest Inventory data.

- Pereira, H.M., Martins, I.S., Rosa, I.M.D., Kim, H., Leadley, P., Popp, A., van Vuuren, D.P., Hurtt, G., Quoss, L., Arneith, A., Baisero, D., Bakkenes, M., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Chini, L., Di Marco, M., Ferrier, S., Fujimori, S., Guerra, C.A., Harfoot, M., Harwood, T.D., Hasegawa, T., Haverd, V., Havlík, P., Hellweg, S., Hilbers, J.P., Hill, S.L.L., Hirata, A., Hoskins, A.J., Humpenöder, F., Janse, J.H., Jetz, W., Johnson, J.A., Krause, A., Leclère, D., Matsui, T., Meijer, J.R., Merow, C., Obersteiner, M., Ohashi, H., De Palma, A., Poulter, B., Purvis, A., Quesada, B., Rondinini, C., Schipper, A.M., Settele, J., Sharp, R., Stehfest, E., Strassburg, B.B.N., Takahashi, K., Talluto, L., Thuiller, W., Titeux, N., Visconti, P., Ware, C., Wolf, F., Alkemade, R., (2024). Global trends and scenarios for terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem services from 1900 to 2050. *Science* 384, 458-465. doi:10.1126/science.adn3441
- Schelhaas, M.J., Hengeveld, G., Filipek, S., König, L., Lerink, B., Staritsky, I., de Jong, A., Nabuurs, G.J., (2022). EFISCEN-Space 1.0 model documentation and manual. Wageningen Environmental Research, Report 3220. Wageningen. 57 pp.
- Sotirov, M., Nilsson, J., Beland-Lindahl, K., Pecurul, M., Niedzialkowski, K., Aquilue, N., Nabau J., Roux, J., Uhan, Z., Pezdevšek Malovrh, Š., (2025a). How regulatory target groups would behave towards EU policy change? Forest owner and manager responses to EU biodiversity and climate policy objectives in Germany, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden. *Land Use Policy* (to be submitted).
- Sotirov, M., Pezdevšek Malovrh, Š., A., Beland Lindahl, K., Haase, M., Aquilué, N., Kraxner, F., Krasovskiy, Schepaschenko, D., Johnstone, C., Hajtmarova, S., Niedzialkowski, K., Nieberg, M., Nilsson, J., Nordström, E.M., Paligorov, I., Pecurul, M., Renaud, P., Sorge, S., Uhan, Z. (2025b). Policy and Driver Scenarios of Forest Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration in Europe. BIOCONSENT project report with coherent scenarios for each case study (D.2.1.1). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14949872
- Sotirov, M., Sallnäs, O. Eriksson, L.O. (2019). Forest owner behavioral models. policy changes. and forest management. An agent-based framework for studying the provision of forest ecosystem goods and services at the landscape level. *Forest Policy and Economics*. 103. 79-89.
- Thrasher, B., Wang, W., Michaelis, A., Melton, F., Lee, T., Nemani, R. (2022). NASA Global Daily Downscaled Projections. CMIP6. *Sci Data* 9. 262 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01393-4>
- Thünen-Institut. (2025). Dritte Bundeswaldinventur-Ergebnisdatenbank. <https://bwi.info>
- Trasobares, A., Mola-Yudego, B., Aquilué, N., Ramón González-Olabarria, J., Garcia-Gonzalo, J., García-Valdés, R., De Cáceres, M., (2022). Nationwide climate-sensitive models for stand dynamics and forest scenario simulation. *Forest Ecology and Management* 505, 119909. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119909>
- UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, (2025). Protected Planet: The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) [May 2025 Release]. Cambridge. UK: UNEP-WCMC and IUCN. Available at: <https://www.protectedplanet.net> (accessed 12 May 2025).
- Vangi, E., Dalmonech, D., Morichetti, M., Grieco E., Giannetti, F., D'Amico, G., Nakhavali, M., Chirici, G., Collalti, A. (2024), Stand Age and Climate Change Effects on Carbon Increments and Stock Dynamics, *Forests*, 15, 1120, <https://doi.org/10.3390/f15071120>
- van Vuuren, D.P., Edmonds, J., Kainuma, M., Riahi, K., Thomson, A., Hibbard, K., Hurtt, G.C., Kram, T., Krey, V., Lamarque, J.-F., Masui, T., Meinshausen, M., Nakicenovic, N., Smith, S.J., Rose, S.K., (2011). The representative concentration pathways: an overview. *Climatic Change* 109, 5. 10.1007/s10584-011-0148-z
- Viana-Soto, A., Senf, C., (2025). The European Forest Disturbance Atlas: a forest disturbance monitoring system using the Landsat archive, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 17, 2373–2404, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2373-2025>.
- Viskari, T., Pusa, J., Fer, I., Repo, A., Vira, J., Liski, J., (2022). Calibrating the soil organic carbon model Yasso20 with multiple datasets. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 15, 1735-1752. 10.5194/gmd-15-1735-2022

Annex I: Scenario storylines for the Spanish case study

Scenario 1 (Multifunctional / BAU)

Current national and EU policies aim to ensure multifunctional, sustainable forest use. Despite thirty percent of the territory being under Natura 2000 protection, biodiversity levels are still declining at the regional scale.

Forest Management Plans are encouraged to guide forest owners' management. These plans follow ORGEST silvicultural prescriptions.

Currently, the most common harvesting method is continuous cover (in Spanish: aclareo sucesivo uniforme) and thinning across all size classes. Only environmental forest owners are implementing active practices to boost biodiversity—such as creating microhabitats and allowing natural evolution, often combined with grazing. However, overall traditional forest owners oppose passive management strategies. Their main concept of preservation relates to the general state of the forests. The current composition of tree species is maintained despite the need to adapt to climate change.

Private owners and smallholders produce wood for energy and establish new local chains to incorporate biomass. Wood fuels as an alternative to fossil fuels remain increasingly important in rural areas. Only 20% of the potential is harvested, and aside from plantations (which account for only %), regeneration occurs naturally.

In this context, the regulatory framework of Natura 2000 and forest law guarantees harvesting within the growth limits. Additionally, new subsidies provide financial support for implementing practices to prevent forest fires and other natural disasters. Forest operations depend heavily on access to forest road infrastructure and qualified professionals. Roads are maintained because they play a crucial role in preventing and extinguishing forest fires. The quality of education and training is being improved, but the availability of qualified forest workers is limited due to tough working conditions and a lack of professional social recognition. The public perception of forestry remains negative toward biodiversity. Urban and rural visions of what forests should provide to society are becoming more polarized, leading to more conflicts.

Some rural areas are experiencing a demographic recovery, but most of the inaccessible mountain regions are used for tourism purposes and as second residences.

Scenario 2 (Closer-to-nature management)

Following the conservation objectives set by the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the EU Forest Strategy, national and regional policies prioritize promoting forest biodiversity conservation and restoration, as well as maintaining carbon forest sinks. As a result, current forest management practices are adapted to enhance regulatory forest ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation. Close-to-nature prescriptions are enforced more strictly. Additionally, besides protecting 30% of the territory as protected areas, one-third of these areas are left to natural evolution. When possible, efforts are made to create synergies with eco-tourism and leisure activities.

Closer-to-nature management is promoted to ensure the supply of both wood and forest ecosystem services. BIORGEST prescriptions are strengthened through policy measures to facilitate changes in forest management practices. Generally speaking: i) using harvesting

methods that promote irregularity; ii) increasing the frequency of mixed and low thinning; iii) delaying the final cut while leaving a percentage of trees (10%) to support natural regeneration; and iv) considering microhabitats and deadwood in forests. Tree species diversity is favored over tree size diversity, and natural regeneration is prioritized.

Due to restrictions across the EU, the supply of European wood may not be sufficient to meet demand. Wood prices are rising, and most wood is imported. In some cases, the final cuts could contribute to value-added products like CLT, but overall, the trend will be biomass production having to comply with stricter standards.

There are some changes in the policy tools compared to the BAU. More subsidies are available for allowing forests to undergo natural succession, although only certain groups of forest owners apply for them. Subsidies for forest fire prevention and drought relief will become more important, but only high-risk areas will benefit (e.g., the Pyrenees will be excluded). Improvements in forestry education and training will result in a more qualified workforce, thanks to safer working conditions. This will lead to an increase in available workers. There is also a focus on providing more accessible technical assistance to forest owners.

In contrast to the previous scenario, carbon markets will become well established, helping to cover the costs of joint management forests in specific areas. The CO₂ taxes will also benefit the forestry sector. Additionally, innovations in harvesting operations will reduce the impact on soil quality and biodiversity. Sustainable rural tourism will be promoted, and the use of forests for sports, leisure, and education will be maintained. Conflicts between the social use of forests and biodiversity may increase. Most rural mountain areas do not have a permanent population year-round but are used as second homes. The urban perspective on forests dominates.